

**BOOK OF ABSTRACTS
HYBRID FIFTH ANNUAL
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
RELIGION, CULTURE, AND
PEACE EDUCATION
Thursday-Friday, April 23-24, 2026**

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Rey Ty**

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**Fifth Annual International Conference on Religion, Culture, and Peace Education
Department of Peace Studies (DPS) and
Religion, Culture, and Peace Laboratory (RCPL)
International College, Payap University, Chiang Mai, Thailand**

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

HYBRID FIFTH ANNUAL

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

ON RELIGION, CULTURE, AND

PEACE EDUCATION

Thursday-Friday, April 24-25, 2026

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Religion, Culture, and Peace Laboratory (RCPL)
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2026 Abstracts

Reference	01
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Rey Ty
Title	Critical Integrated Literature Review of Peace Education: From Structural Violence to Normative, Systemic, Decolonial Lenses
Problem Statement	While peace education (P.E.) spreads like wildfire, the complex field is theoretically fragmented. There is structural blindness to inequality and gap in practice for social transformation.
Research Questions or Objectives	This article discusses the following: RQ1: What are the major paradigms in peace education? RQ2: Why are there paradigm shifts in peace education? RQ3: How can an integrated framework promote social change?
Literature, Concept and Theory	Literature that impacted peace education included structural violence (Galtung), critical pedagogy and liberation (Freire), relational conflict transformation (Lederach), hegemony and ideology (Gramsci), decolonial epistemology (Fanon), reproduction and inequality (Bourdieu), political economy (Adam Smith; Ricardo; Marx), and systems analysis (Bertalanffy; Easton; Senge).
Research Methods	This article is grounded in the constructivist paradigm for meaning making, contextual understanding, and theoretical interpretation (Cresswell). It employs an integrative literature review (Torraco), combing through peace education publications and weaving themes together. It inductively reveals changing trends through conceptual mapping and theoretical synthesis.
Summary Findings	RQ1: These are the changing themes: normative (Reardon), critical PE (Bajaj), structural turn (Kester), Institutional PE (Jenkins), political economy (Novelli), complex systems thinking (O'Connor), and decolonial PE (Kester). RQ2: Paradigm shifts occurred as approaches to P.E. changed: from norms to critical consciousness, institutions, and systems thinking. Political economy framework grounds P.E. not on ideas but on material realities. RQ3: Transformation requires the integration of interventions in pedagogy, structures, and systems.
Conclusion and Recommendation	P.E. has evolved as a result of recognition of structural violence and complexity. Political economy forces P.E. to investigate social conditions and not merely stay in the realm of ideas. Social change requires integration of ethical, structural, system frameworks, not in silos.
Keywords	Decolonial, Critical, Peace Education, Political Economy
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	Yes
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education
Education	Formal Education

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Reference Number	02
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	BRYAN FLORO
Title	Reconciling The Concept of Peace and Violence From “Above” And “Below” Towards the Development of a Contextualized Peace Education Framework
Problem Statement	This study examines how the differing understandings of peace and violence held by former NPA rebels and government personnel can be reconciled to develop a contextualized peace education framework. The study aims to develop a locally grounded contextualized peace education framework in Bataan by using the experiences and conflict conditions in former CPP-NPA-affected communities to guide sustainable and culturally responsive peacebuilding programs.
Research Questions or Objectives	The study aims to develop a locally grounded contextualized peace education framework in Bataan by using the experiences and conflict conditions in former CPP-NPA-affected communities to guide sustainable and culturally responsive peacebuilding programs.
Literature, Concept and Theory	The study is anchored on Marx’s Class Conflict Theory, Gurr’s Relative Deprivation Theory, and Galtung’s Theory of Violence and Peace to explain the roots of violence and differing perceptions of peace.
Research Methods	The study is anchored on Marx’s Class Conflict Theory, Gurr’s Relative Deprivation Theory, and Galtung’s Theory of Violence and Peace to explain the roots of violence and differing perceptions of peace
Summary Findings	The Contextualized Peace Education Framework promotes a culture of peace in Bataan by grounding teaching and learning in local conflict realities, empowering learners with critical understanding, human rights values, and nonviolent problem-solving skills for sustainable community peacebuilding.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The findings show that a contextualized peace education framework grounded in local lived experiences effectively develops students’ critical understanding, values, and skills to address conflict and promote a sustainable culture of peace.
Keywords	Contextualized peace education, Education for peace, Peace Bottom-up perspective (from “Below”), Peace education framework, Reconciliation
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education
Education	Constructivist Education

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Reference Number	03 / 06/ 10 / 62
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	John Rovic Pizarro, John Paul Santos, Toni Ann H. Laguna
Title	Contextualizing Social Justice Issues in Social Studies Education in a Teacher Education Institution
Problem Statement	Aside from the problem that social studies are perceived as boring and full of abstract concepts, teaching social justice issues in classroom seems more theoretical than practical, thus neglecting the praxis in resolving conflicts related to race, culture, religion, and other concepts in teaching social studies.
Research Questions or Objectives	The main focus of the study aims to 1) explore the teachers' definition and understanding of social justice issues, 2) teachers' contextualization and integration practices of social justice issues in social studies, and 3) teachers' challenges and constraints of contextualizing social justice issues in social studies.
Literature, Concept and Theory	The Critical Theory by Max Horkheimer serves as the main theoretical lens of the study as it explains the goal of achieving human emancipation from the things, events, and even circumstances that enslave people. It is highly relevant to the study because it provides a framework for examining the hidden curricula and power structures within educational systems that arise within classrooms itself.
Research Methods	The qualitative case study design of the paper used data triangulation including in-depth semi-structured interviews and was analyzed by using Martin Heidegger's Interpretive Phenomenology Analysis (IPA) to interpret the data.
Summary Findings	The findings revealed that 1) social justice issues are defined by the necessary systemic and material conditions, grounded in ethical and relational mandate required for a shared world, the teacher's professional duty in relation to justice, and the unconcealedness of the problem's systemic and structural nature, 2) the contextualization and integration practices of social justice issues in Social Studies involve argumentative discourse and other activities that considers their lived experiences, and 3) challenges proved that there is limited institutional support and budget deficit which leads to poor conditions in contextualizing; curriculum constraints and failure were also highlighted which contributes to the hindrances faced by the teachers.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Social justice is the highest form of justice and "The Social Justice Teaching Framework" may be utilized by teachers for better contextualization of social justice issues in social studies education.
Keywords	Contextualization, Education, Integration, Social Justice, Social Studies
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Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Education, Justice and Peace
Education	Social Justice Education

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Reference Number	04
Types of Presentation	10-minute max NON-Academic Presentation
Name	John Rovic Pizarro
Title	Church Confessions Collection
Problem Statement	Gaps of Christianity and the Indoctrination of Religion, together with social issues.
Research Questions or Objectives	The focus of the poetry collection is to explore the clerical perspectives of church leaders and figures, as well as to critique them for social change.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Medieval, Renaissance, and the Enlightenment Period
Research Methods	Poetry Collections (10 Poems in total)
Summary Findings	Poetry Collections
Conclusion and Recommendation	
Keywords	Christianity, Philosophy, Roman Catholicism, Social Issues, Theology
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Religion, Justice and Peace
Education	Collective Learning

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Reference Number	05
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Juichiro Tanabe
Title	Buddhist AI Ethics for Peaceful and Harmonious Designing, Development, and Deployment of AI
Problem Statement	What is often neglected in AI ethics is the analysis of the relational dynamics between human mind and the use of AI.
Research Questions or Objectives	The research examines a Buddhist ethical, socio-political, and philosophical implications of Artificial Intelligence for peace.
Literature, Concept and Theory	The research is based on Buddhist philosophy, AI ethics, and peace theory.
Research Methods	Critical literature reviews
Summary Findings	Ethics of mindfulness and dialogue among all stakeholders empower them to manage the possible harmful use of AI while dialogue helps them to enhance mutual understanding and collaborative AI development.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The integrating mindfulness practices with dialogical forms of global governance entailing both state and non-state actors can empower them to hone self-critique and expand their epistemological and ontological horizons, to jointly design, develop, and deploy AI for humane and peaceful coexistence.
Keywords	AI Ethics, Buddhism, Dialogue, Mindfulness, Relational self
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General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Moral Education

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Reference Number	07
Types of Presentation	ATTEND ONLY.
Name	SAW LALBWEL HTOO
Title	An Analysis of the Economic Gap between Rohingya Refugees and Host Communities in Cox's Bazar after 2021 Myanmar Coup
Problem Statement	The fundamental problem is a widening "capability gap": Rohingya refugees are trapped in a cycle of aid-dependency with zero legal agency, while host communities face market-driven precarity and wage depression (World Bank, 2024). Despite billions in humanitarian spending, there is a lack of econometric evidence explaining how this structural divergence affects humanitarian assistance and long-term economic resilience for either group (WFP, 2025). Without quantifying this gap, policy interventions remain "blind" to the true cost of statelessness and the erosion of human capabilities in a post-coup environment (Sen, 1999).
Research Questions or Objectives	This study aims to quantify the magnitude of the humanitarian assistance gap between Rohingya refugees and host communities using Propensity Score Matching to isolate legal status as a primary driver of horizontal inequality. Additionally, it seeks to evaluate how external funding shocks post-2021 have differentially impacted the economic resilience of both groups to propose evidence-based policy reforms under the ICESCR framework.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Conflict: Understanding Group Violence in Multiethnic Societies. Palgrave Macmillan. (Foundational text for Group-based Inequality). Betts, A., & Collier, P. (2017). Refuge: Transforming a Broken Refugee System. Oxford University Press. (Analyzes the shift from aid-dependency to self-reliance). Zaman, S., & Haque, M. (2023). Political instability in Myanmar and its economic spillovers on the Rohingya-host ecosystem. <i>Asian Economic Review</i> , 41(1), 88–105. (Links the Myanmar Coup to regional shocks). Miller, S., & Sullivan, K. (2023). Beyond calories: The econometric challenge of measuring nutritional agency in protracted displacement. <i>World Development</i> , 165, 106–121. World Bank. (2024). <i>The Long Shadow of Displacement: Socioeconomic Trends in Cox's Bazar (2021–2024)</i> . World Bank Group. (Primary source for Post-Coup Panel Data). WFP (World Food Programme). (2025). <i>Resource Prioritization in Protracted Crisis: A Comparative Analysis of Humanitarian Assistance</i> . United Nations
Research Methods	Propensity Score Matching (PSM), Probit/ Logit Model
Summary Findings	The study anticipates a statistically significant "Humanitarian Assistance Gap," showing that while refugees receive higher in-kind aid volumes, their lack of market access results in significantly lower economic agency compared to the host community.
Conclusion and Recommendation	This research is to advocate policymakers for refugee economic justice through International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) and to implement area-based programming to bolster host community resilience and regional social cohesion.
Keywords	Economic Justice, Horizontal Inequality, Humanitarian Agency Gap, Propensity Score Matching (PSM), Rohingya
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
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Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Workplace Learning

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Reference Number	08
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Sa Nehru
Title	Exploring the Role of Christian Youth Leaders in Promoting Peace in Myanmar: Challenges and Opportunities
Problem Statement	Myanmar Christian youth leaders are actively engaged in the community, social welfare and religious affairs but less promoting and advocating the culture of peace.
Research Questions or Objectives	The objective of this study is to examine the role of Christian youth leaders in promoting peace in Myanmar, and to identify the challenges and opportunities that influence their peacebuilding efforts.
Literature, Concept and Theory	UNESCO (Formal, Nonformal, Informal) , Transformative Learning Theory and Andragogy
Research Methods	The expected opportunities for Christian youth leaders are to have social influence, community leadership roles and high levels of trust in their communities. However, they may be taking the risk of security concerns, the threat of political instability, and their limited capacity and the gaps of understanding the peace culture and peace education.
Summary Findings	The expected opportunities for Christian youth leaders are to have social influence, community leadership roles and high levels of trust in their communities. However, they may be taking the risk of security concerns, the threat of political instability, and their limited capacity and the gaps of understanding the peace culture and peace education.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Through networking and systematic collaboration among Christian youth leaders, they will be actively engaged in promoting peace and practicing peace culture.
Keywords	Christianity, Myanmar, Peace Education, Religious Leaders, Youths
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
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Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Religion
Education	Skills Development

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Reference Number	09 / 63 / 64
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	France Ruwie Eala, Hazel Anjela Mei C. Peña, Jhanna Mel Reyes
Title	Understanding Peace Through The Lens Of Pre-Service Teachers: Development Of A Contextualized Peace Education Framework
Problem Statement	This study aims to understand peace through the lens of pre-service teachers (PSTs) at BPSU–Balanga Campus in development of a contextualized peace education framework.
Research Questions or Objectives	It describes the respondents’ profile, their knowledge in selected peace education topics, differences in knowledge when grouped by sex, age, and program major, their peace attitudes, values, and conflict resolution skills influencing knowledge, their classroom and community peace practices, and the proposed contextualized framework.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Existing literature indicates that peace education is shaped by varied context-based approaches, underscoring the need for regional contextualization.
Research Methods	The study employed a convergent parallel mixed methods design using a survey (n = 166) and focus group discussions (n = 17), with quantitative data analyzed through statistical tools and qualitative data examined using Braun and Clarke’s (2006) thematic analysis.
Summary Findings	Findings show that most PSTs were 20–24 years old, female, and English majors with strong peace attitudes, values, skills, and high knowledge, no significant differences by sex, age, or program major, a strong influence of peace values and conflict resolution skills on knowledge, strong practices in three domains but limitations in two, and the development of a five-domain contextualized framework.
Conclusion and Recommendation	It is recommended that the proposed framework be validated using data from other populations.
Keywords	Bataan Peninsula State University, contextualized peace education framework, peace education, pre-service teachers, teacher education institutions
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Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Education
Education	Skills Enhancement

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Reference Number	11
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Zaw Lin
Title	Barriers of Accessing Education in EROs' Areas in Myanmar After the 2021 Military Coup
Problem Statement	Most research scholars in post 2021 have stated that Military junta's education is considered as slave education in Myanmar (Spreelung et al., 2024, p.74)
Research Questions or Objectives	(1) To identify the barriers on accessing education in EROs' areas in Myanmar after the 2021 military coup; (2) To analyze the main causes of the barriers; (3) To explore the ongoing status that can persist the barriers
Literature, Concept and Theory	The literature covers two themes: the decentralization of education and the lack of equity to access education (Wong et al., 2024). Concepts covered are Education in post- 2021 military coup in Myanmar
Research Methods	A secondary qualitative research method through case studies and data was analyzed through thematic analysis
Summary Findings	RQ1: Improving civilians' capacity by coordinating between EROs and the NUG to overcome the barriers. RQ2: Aware of potential risks to reduce the barriers. RQ3: Strengthening existing reformed education to be protected with policies and laws.
Conclusion and Recommendation	It is important for ensuring safety concern of the students, requiring access to higher education and advanced alternative approaches, maintaining and protecting own curriculum with policies and laws. International recognition and accreditation, funding raising activities, investment in future digital learning, maintaining and upgrading MTB-MLE programs, coordination and collaboration among EROs are required.
Keywords	Accessing Education, Barriers, EROs, Myanmar and Post-Military Coup
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
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General Area	Education, Justice and Peace
Education	Social Justice Education

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Reference Number	12
Types of Presentation	Attend Only
Name	Ye Lin Maw
Title	Colonial Law as Structural Violence: Myanmar's Penal Code vs ICCPR
Problem Statement	The continued use of Myanmar's colonial era Penal Code, designed primarily for control, conflicts with modern human rights standards, creating structural violence that impedes the transition to sustainable peace.
Research Questions or Objectives	1) To identify specific high-impact Penal Code provisions that conflict with the ICCPR.) 2) To demonstrate how the Penal Code's mechanism enables structural violence against activists using empirical case data. 3) To determine why this colonial legal framework acts as a systemic barrier to positive peace.
Literature, Concept and Theory	The following concepts and theories were used: Structural Violence (Galtung, 1969), Positive Peace (Barash & Webel, 2022), Postcolonial Legal Theory, and Customary International Law (jus cogens).
Research Methods	This study used Qualitative textual analysis, Comparative legal analysis (Penal Code vs. ICCPR), and Case Mapping Analysis using AAPP-Burma data.
Summary Findings	1) Five high impact Penal code provisions textually violate ICCPR Articles. 2) The laws institutionalizing arbitrary arrest (CrPC§54) and criminalizing dissent (PS§505), with over 14,000 documented cases. 3) Legal continuity blocking the rule of law foundation needed for positive peace.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The Penal Code is a profound legal barrier that actively sustains authoritarian control. Dismantling this colonial legacy is essential for transitioning Myanmar towards a justice-based and sustainable peace. Recommend the immediate legislative repeal/amendment of high-conflict sections and the establishment of an Independent Legal Review Commission to vet colonial laws.
Keywords	Colonial Legacy, Human Rights, Myanmar, Penal Code, Structural Violence
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Activist Education

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Reference Number	13
Types of Presentation	Attend Only
Name	Aung Ko Khant
Title	International Human Rights Intervention and Accountability in Post-Coup Myanmar
Problem Statement	After the 2021 military coup, Myanmar faced serious human rights violations. International laws exist to protect civilians, but interventions have had limited effect. Political and enforcement problems make it hard to hold the military accountable
Research Questions or Objectives	1. Identify what international human rights interventions happened in Myanmar after the coup. 2. Examine how these interventions affected accountability. 3. Explore why these interventions have not fully protected civilians.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Dembour (2010) – Four schools of human rights, Sen (2009) – Human dignity and justice, Theories of international intervention UN, ICC, and ASEAN responses, Local documentation
Research Methods	Qualitative analysis, Reviewing UN, ICC, ASEAN, and NGO reports, Comparing different international responses, Thematic analysis
Summary Findings	1. International interventions exist but are limited, slow, and not well-coordinated. 2. Political and enforcement problems make accountability weak. 3. Structural and regional issues prevent justice and sustainable protection.
Conclusion and Recommendation	International actions in post-coup Myanmar are not enough to stop violations. UN, ICC, and ASEAN document crimes, but political limits reduce their effect. Hybrid justice approaches and support for local documentation can improve protection and accountability.
Keywords	Accountability, Human Rights, International Law, Intervention, Myanmar
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
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General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Humanist Education

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Reference Number	14
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Khine Myo Linn
Title	Civil Society Organizations in Promoting Human Rights in Rakhine State after the 2021 Coup
Problem Statement	CSOs lost their working space after the 2021 coup. Many activists were arrested or had to hide. Restrictions and internet cuts made communication difficult. Conflict in Rakhine made the situation worse. CSOs still promote human rights and civic education despite the risks.
Research Questions or Objectives	1) To identify the roles of CSOs in promoting human rights after the coup 2) To explore how CSOs adjust their strategies to continue human rights work in difficult conditions 3) To understand why CSOs are important for strengthening communities and empowering people
Literature, Concept and Theory	Human Rights-Based Approach (UNDP, 2006), Empowerment Theory (Zimmerman, 1995), Civil Society (Ashley South, 2018)
Research Methods	Qualitative method, secondary research from reports, informal dialogue and informal observation with my friends' residence.
Summary Findings	1.CSOs raise public awareness on human rights and justice. 2.CSOs adapt by using informal networks, safer labels, and stronger digital security. 3.CSOs teach communities to understand their rights, build confidence and stay united.
Conclusion and Recommendation	CSOs in Rakhine continue to defend human rights after the 2021 coup. They provide humanitarian, educational, and advocacy support. Their work keeps dignity, justice, and democracy alive. Their documentation will help with future truth and accountability efforts.
Keywords	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Human Rights, Community Empowerment, Rakhine State, Civic Education
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
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Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Humanist Education

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Reference Number	15
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Saw Zadkiel Eh-Kwee
Title	Peace Education Perspectives of Ethnic Administration Organizations in Post-Coup Myanmar
Problem Statement	Theory-driven understanding of how ethnic administrative organizations in Myanmar conceptualize and enact peace education, across the forms of peace, and internal and external dimensions of peace, in their current education regimes and political projects (Auh & Kim, 2025; South & Lall, 2016).
Research Questions or Objectives	1) To identify and describe the forms of peace knowledge, peace values, and peace skills are reported in the studies of ethnic education and peace education in Myanmar. 2) To examine how internal and external dimensions of peace portrayed in the literature on ethnic administrative organizations' education policies and programs in Myanmar. 3) To explore the reasons why historical grievances, justice claims, and evolving political roles appear in the literature as key factors shaping ethnic administrative organizations' peace education orientations in Myanmar.
Literature, Concept and Theory	1. Peace Education Theory - (Reardon, 2004); Applicable in Myanmar by providing core dimensions of peace knowledge, values, and skills in EAO curricula 2. EAOs as governance or justice providers and political actors - Asia Foundation reports; ethnic-armed actors and justice provision 3. Ethnic education regimes and federalism imaginaries - (South & Lall, 2016); ethnic education and peace process in Myanmar 4. Critical peace education, structural and epistemic violence - (Bajaj, 2008); critical perspectives on peace education policy 5. Decolonial peace and knowledge production - (Mac Ginty & Richmond, 2013); critical peacebuilding
Research Methods	Study used narrative review research design, analyzing academic and grey literatures, reports and publications from reputable institutions and websites, to gather information supporting the objective of the study.
Summary Findings	1) Studies suggest ethnic minority education produces peace knowledge, values, and skills rooted in ethno historical suffering, rights claims, coexistence imaginaries, dignity, self-determination, solidarity, and political negotiation. 2) Preliminary findings suggest EAOs use education to reduce direct violence, foster intra ethnic unity and inter-ethnic coexistence, and pursue convergent, context dependent peace programs engaging state systems. 3) Preliminary evidence suggests EAO peace education reflects distinct histories of conflict and ceasefire, shaping integrated initiatives and claims to legitimacy, governance capacity, and roles in a future federal Myanmar.
Conclusion and Recommendation	This article is expected to underscore the significance of workplace learning and cultural sensitivity for successful logistic customer service in hotels.
Keywords	Ethnic Administration Organizations, Peace Education, Peace Education Perspectives, Post-coup Myanmar
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Justice and Peace
Education	Workplace Learning

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Reference Number	16
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Si Thu Maung Maung
Title	Human Rights and Peacebuilding in Ethnically Divided Myanmar (1991–2020)
Problem Statement	Myanmar’s peacebuilding efforts emphasize reconciliation but often neglect justice, accountability, and inclusivity, resulting in fragile and unsustainable peace outcomes.
Research Questions or Objectives	To examine the relationship between human-rights principles and peacebuilding practices in Myanmar. To analyze how human-rights norms and mechanisms contribute to reconciliation and structural transformation. To evaluate why justice and accountability are essential for reconstructing positive peace in ethnically divided societies
Literature, Concept and Theory	Dembour’s (2010) Four Schools of Human Rights, Galtung’s (1969) Positive Peace, Lederach’s (1997) Conflict Transformation, Sen’s (2009) Human Dignity and Justice, and Azar’s (1990) Protracted Social Conflict.
Research Methods	This research adopts a qualitative documentary approach, using historical and thematic analysis of peace agreements, civil-society documents, and NGO reports from 1991 to 2020.
Summary Findings	Human rights and peacebuilding are interdependent but remain institutionally separated. Integrating rights enhances both structural (policy reform) and relational (trust-building) peace. Justice and accountability strengthen reconciliation by addressing exclusion and restoring dignity.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The study highlights that sustainable peace in Myanmar requires embedding human-rights principles of justice, inclusion, and accountability within all peacebuilding frameworks to achieve positive peace and genuine reconciliation.
Keywords	Conflict, Ethnicity, Human Rights, Peacebuilding, Reconciliation
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Humanist Education

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Reference Number	17
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Wiint Wah Htun
Title	Andragogy in Peace Education: Supporting Mental Wellbeing and Grassroots Peacebuilding in Post-Coup Kayah State, Myanmar
Problem Statement	Kayah State is facing conflict, displacement, education disruption, and mental health problems. Community education programs have been created, but there is limited research on how andragogy plays in these programs and how it helps wellbeing and peacebuilding.
Research Questions or Objectives	1) To know how andragogy is supported in peace education 2) To examine how education helps mental wellbeing 3) To analyze the role of youth in grassroots peacebuilding
Literature, Concept and Theory	Andragogy (Knowles,2020), Peacebuilding (Lederach,1997), Mental wellbeing (Ungar,2011)
Research Methods	This study used documentary research design, using news articles, books, and NGO reports to gather information
Summary Findings	1) To support youth, learn better and provide their experiences. They shape their own learning activities. 2) To help people feel safe and supported. They build trust and cooperation. 3) To encourage youth participation in grassroots peacebuilding
Conclusion and Recommendation	Communities based-educations systems have created their own learning spaces during conflict in Kayah State. These programs help both education and emotional wellbeing. Andragogy supports how this learning works in the grassroots peace building process. Community education programs need more support. Peace education should include mental health support. Youth should be leadership roles. Scholars should focus on ethnic such as Kayah State.
Keywords	Andragogy, Grassroots Peacebuilding, Mental Wellbeing, Peace Education, Post-coup Kayah State
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Religion, Culture, Justice and Peace
Education	Pedagogy

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Reference Number	18
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Si Thu Maung Maung
Title	Peace Education in reducing conflict in Myanmar's post 2021 context
Problem Statement	Conflict continues partly because many people lack skills in dialogue, empathy, and peaceful conflict resolution.
Research Questions or Objectives	Peace education can contribute to reducing conflict by encouraging nonviolent approaches and mutual understanding. Peace education influences attitudes by developing empathy, dialogue skills, and critical thinking. Peace education is important for sustainable peace because it addresses deeper causes of division, such as prejudice and mistrust.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Peace education (Harris, 2004; Reardon, 1988) Positive peace (Galtung, 1996) Conflict transformation (Lederach, 1997)
Research Methods	Literature review, Conceptual analysis
Summary Findings	Peace education can contribute to reducing conflict by encouraging nonviolent approaches and mutual understanding. Peace education influences attitudes by developing empathy, dialogue skills, and critical thinking. Peace education is important for sustainable peace because it addresses deeper causes of division, such as prejudice and mistrust.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Integrating peace education elements into formal and non-formal learning Encouraging dialogue-based teaching methods Supporting youth-focused peace initiatives in divided communities
Keywords	Conflict, Dialogue, Education, Peacebuilding, Reconciliation
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Education

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Reference Number	19
Types of Presentation	Attend Only
Name	YAN MYO NAING
Title	Peace Education: A Literature Review
Problem Statement	The Role of Proverbs and Adages in Shaping Burmese Society
Research Questions or Objectives	Burmese society lived in fear which has limited the freedom of thought. Some proverbs and adages discourage criticizing societal practices and act as obstacles to the development of individuals and society. Example: မလုပ် ၊ မရှုပ် ၊ မပြုတ် (If you don't do anything, you won't get into trouble, and you won't get fired.)
Literature, Concept and Theory	Conceptual non-empirical article in humanities or philosophy
Research Methods	1.Transformative Learning Theory 2. Burmese Political Values 3. Proverbs Are The Best Policy 4. Sociolinguistics
Summary Findings	1. Identify positive and negative influences 2. Promote critical thinking 3. Change thought and behavior
Conclusion and Recommendation	Proverbs and adages which guide morality, wisdom and lifestyle.
Keywords	Culture, Education, Freedom, Myanmar, Proverb
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Culture
Education	Traditional Education

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Reference Number	20
Types of Presentation	Attend Only
Name	Myo Aung
Title	An analysis of peace education components in Dhamma Talks by Myanmar Buddhist Monks
Problem Statement	Dhamma talk, which is the main way to disseminate the Buddha's teachings to its believers seem considerable as a kind of peace education. But it is doubtful to consider when we look at its themes, teaching tradition, and practices.
Research Questions or Objectives	To analyze the components of peace education in Dhamma Talk by Myanmar monks
Literature, Concept and Theory	Peace Education Transformative Learning (Mezirow) Dhamma
Research Methods	This study will use a qualitative research design, thematic analysis, and purposive sampling. Dhamma Talk Audio /Video (20 – 30 Max) online will be collected and analyzed, and a total of 6 informal conversations (3 Laymen and 3 monks max) will be conducted.
Summary Findings	Comparative analysis of the components of Dhamma talk and Peace Education
Conclusion and Recommendation	Need to improve the themes and method of Dhamma Talk in peace educational purpose systemically to be affective dissemination and outcome.
Keywords	Buddhist Monk, Dhamma Talk, Myanmar, Peace Education, Religion
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Education, Religion
Education	Moral Education

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Reference Number	21
Types of Presentation	Attend Only
Name	Le Cho Tha
Title	
Problem Statement	
Research Questions or Objectives	
Literature, Concept and Theory	
Research Methods	
Summary Findings	
Conclusion and Recommendation	
Keywords	
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	None
Education	

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Reference Number	22
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Nay Hein Phyo
Title	Peace Education Barriers in Karenni Internally Displaced Persons Contexts
Problem Statement	Local CSOs play critical roles in supporting IDPs, yet their human rights advocacy faces severe restrictions, insecurity, and resource limitations under Myanmar's military regime.
Research Questions or Objectives	1. To identify the roles of local CSOs in protecting IDPs' human rights. 2. To examine how these CSOs implement and sustain human rights work amid operational challenges. 3. To analyze the importance of CSOs in sustaining rights protection where the state has failed.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Human Rights Theory (Donnelly, 2013), Civil Society Theory (Keane, 2009), Human Security (UNDP, 1994), and Local Governance in New Wars (Kaldor, 2012)
Research Methods	Qualitative method, secondary data, document review, thematic analysis, secondary research from reports, informal dialogue.
Summary Findings	CSOs provide essential humanitarian aid as de facto rights providers. They overcome challenges through trust-based, decentralized networks and adaptive strategies. Their resilience sustains human dignity and accountability amid state failure.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Local CSOs are indispensable protectors of IDP human rights in Karenni State, bridging humanitarian gaps and sustaining rights-based governance despite conflict and repression.
Keywords	Civil Society, Human Rights, IDPs, Protections of IDPs, Karenni State
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Humanist Education

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Reference Number	23
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Sai Tun Aung Lwin
Title	Liberalization without transformation: The failure of Liberal Peace building in Myanmar
Problem Statement	Myanmar had faced failed democratization and liberal peace within the past ten years. Onward, almost 5 years after the post-2021 coup turmoil, how to resume Democratization and liberal peace is an intractable problem so far. As the post-coup conflict in Myanmar has reached a stalemate, the possibility of less than outright victory and how to restore peace is a matter of necessity.
Research Questions or Objectives	Myanmar had faced failed Democratization and liberal peace within the past ten years. According to lessons learned from countries that have failed Liberal Peace, there exists a liberal peace dilemma: If you liberalize too quickly and elections can deepen old hostilities. If you delay democratization, authoritarian elites may consolidate power. This is the “peace–democracy dilemma.”
Literature, Concept and Theory	Peace Studies, Liberal Peace, Conflict transformation, Dilemma of the top-down approach. Motivation: My interest in peace and conflict issues dates back to my childhood. I grew up in Shan State, which was prone to war and conflicts. From an early age, I realized the importance of peace. From my early career journalism to my later career (Consultant, Analyst, Researcher at various Organizations), I managed to get a chance to observe, witness, and analyze work.
Research Methods	1. Qualitative Research, 2. Research method and rely on exploratory and explanatory methods. To examine this issue, based on my past experience as witnessed, observed, and covered the past decade peace process (From Journalist, analyst, observer, and peace process supporting team).
Summary Findings	Authoritarian characters of the Myanmar ruler blocs (Military and Civilian Government) halted the Liberal peace process in Myanmar. Like many failures in liberal peace around the world, Myanmar is not unique. Many countries brought democracy as a solution to end the war. But democratization to end a war is a different route than democracy as an agreed solution. Myanmar's problem is an attempt at democratization while trying to end a war. Democracy was not the end product of conflict resolution. Worse, democratization was a hybrid system that was more conflict-prone than autocracy and full democracy in Myanmar. In fact, liberal peace needs meaningful political pluralism, fair elections, rule of law, civilian oversight, and protection of rights.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The need for liberal peace is the rule of law, functioning institutions, a monopoly on legitimate violence, and predictable governance. Without organizing numerous and scattered groups, that is, warlordism, which would directly undermine the pillars of liberal peace and Myanmar’s so-called resistance movement.
Keywords	Liberal Peace, Failed-Democratization, Transition, Power Sharing, Competitiveness Authoritarian
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Activist Education

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Reference Number	24
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Sergio Quiroga
Title	Art and Science for Environmental Transformation: A Citizen Communication Experience
Problem Statement	The La Ribera housing complex in Villa Mercedes (San Luis, Argentina) faces numerous environmental problems: garbage accumulation, urban pests, sewage overflows, a lack of urban trees, and limited environmental information available to the community. These problems are compounded by low levels of organized citizen participation, despite residents' interest in getting involved.
Research Questions or Objectives	This project aims to design and implement an interdisciplinary educational strategy, led by high school students, that integrates art, science, and technology (STEAM approach) to raise awareness of local environmental issues, promote citizen participation, and empower students as agents of social transformation through the production of communication and artistic materials with community impact.
Literature, Concept and Theory	This pedagogical proposal integrates multiple theoretical perspectives to construct a transformative educational experience. Drawing from critical pedagogy, as developed by Paulo Freire (1970, 1984, 1997) and Henry Giroux (1983, 2001, 2011, 2014), the approach positions students not as passive recipients but as active knowledge producers and critical citizens capable of intervening in and transforming their reality. The environmental dimension is further enriched by the perspectives of Enrique Leff (2004) on environmental rationality and Moacir Gadotti (2000) on Earth pedagogy, fostering an ecological consciousness that challenges hegemonic models of development. This content is explored through an interdisciplinary STEAM approach (Bybee, 2013), integrating science, technology, engineering, art, and mathematics to address real-world problems creatively. Finally, the process of meaning-making is understood through the communication theories of Mario Kaplún (1998), who advocates for a dialogic pedagogy of communication.
Research Methods	The methodological design adopted responds to the principles of participatory action research, articulated with the Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology, which allowed the 5th year "D" students of EPA No. 10 (Villa Mercedes) to be involved as active protagonists in the transformation of their environment during the period May-December 2025.
Summary Findings	The environmental assessment, based on a survey of 147 residents, revealed a majority perception of the neighborhood as "fair" (54.4%), with key problems such as accumulated garbage (55.1%), pests (50.3%), and water pollution (38.1%), along with a strong demand for tree planting (65.3%) and a significant lack of graphic and digital environmental information (88.4%), although incipient recycling practices persist (only 25.2% always separate waste).
Conclusion and Recommendation	Based on the project's results and lessons learned, recommendations are formulated for various key stakeholders to ensure its sustainability and amplify its impact. For schools, it is suggested that the "Green Voices" methodology be institutionalized as a permanent tool for interdisciplinary work, that the model be extended to other courses and socio-environmental issues, that a school network of youth environmental monitors be created, and that the process be systematically documented to create replicable teaching materials for future iterations.
Keywords	Active citizenship, Community socio-environmental transformation, Participatory environmental education, STEAM artistic communication, Youth empowerment
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	Yes, I have a doctorate, and I publish empirical social papers.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Education
Education	Experiential Learning

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Reference Number	25
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Violet B. Valdez, Mon Mon Myat
Title	Teaching Documentary Filmmaking as Social A Yangon Film School
Problem Statement	It is a descriptive case study of education in conflict setting with the focus on Yangon Film School (Yangon, Myanmar) in a setting of protracted civil conflict that has persisted since 1968.
Research Questions or Objectives	It examined the school's approach in the teaching of documentary filmmaking and analyzed key aspects of the school's operations by using a descriptive case study method.
Literature, Concept and Theory	The approach to the teaching of documentary filmmaking is informed by the conceptualization of this media genre as an artistic form of storytelling that pursues social advocacy and as a form of journalistic narrative, albeit with a viewpoint (Kuhn and Westwell 2012; Johnson 2011; Combs and Combs 2013; Aufderheide 2007).
Research Methods	The study used the methodology of a descriptive case study wherein a social phenomenon is portrayed in detail in its real-world context using techniques of data collection. Data was drawn from a qualitative analysis of in-depth interviews of two key informants, the school's annual reports from 2007 to 2018, the report of an external evaluator commissioned by the European Union, and course syllabi.
Summary Findings	The school's faculty consisted of a pool of foreign experts, none of whom served full time. The school's dependence on grants posed challenges such as restrictions on course offerings due to funding shortfalls, and the program's long-term sustainability. To meet these challenges and realize the vision of an eventual turnover of the school's management to locals, the course "Teach to Train" was offered to advanced students.
Conclusion and Recommendation	How do the student's documentary films fit in the mold of social advocacy cinema? The production of films that critique social injustices also raises questions as to whose voices are privileged for dissemination. It could also be asked what media ethics guide the school in the decisions it makes about the production of documentary films. The question of the social impact of the films ought to be investigated in greater depth. It is important to examine these claims and understand the social processes involved in any impact the films could have had.
Keywords	documentary filmmaking, education in conflict setting, military dictatorship, social advocacy cinema, participatory filmmaking
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Education
Education	Teaching Methodologies

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Reference Number	26
Types of Presentation	10-minute max NON-Academic Presentation
Name	Hans Hansen
Title	The Pilgrim's Path to Peace
Problem Statement	How pilgrimage creates peace in the world
Research Questions or Objectives	The Camino de Santiago creates profound internal changes in humans through simple external activity, more than just a hike or a holiday in the south of Europe.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Millions walked the "Camino de Santiago" over centuries. What is it about, how does it connect anyone to the divine? Who walks it and why? What lessons are there to learn when experiencing the pilgrimage?
Research Methods	Video Interviews with random pilgrims and volunteers on the Camino de Santiago.
Summary Findings	Summarized video of main findings and talking points related to a series of video interviews with pilgrims for the YouTube Channel @talkingtonsource.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Finding your true Self by walking away from your false self: Life itself is a Pilgrimage.
Keywords	experiences, life, peace, pilgrimage, spirituality
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Religion, Culture, Justice and Peace
Education	Learning Process

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Reference Number	27
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	HADJE CRESENCIO SADJE
Title	Peace Education After Savagery: Decolonizing Peace in the Time of Genocide
Problem Statement	In an era marked by genocidal violence and the collapse of the post-World War II international moral order, can peace education remain credible without fundamentally decolonizing its philosophical foundations? When the very civilization that claims universality reveals itself as a metaphysics of barbarism masked by appeals to progress and humanity, what pedagogical frameworks remain adequate for educating toward peace?
Research Questions or Objectives	To critically examine how the philosophical foundations of Western peace education are rendered untenable by the genocidal violence in Gaza and to articulate a decolonized, combative pedagogy rooted in Palestinian experience and transnational solidarity.
Literature, Concept and Theory	This paper engages three interrelated theoretical frameworks. First, it draws on Hamid Dabashi's <i>After Savagery</i> , which argues that Israel's assault on Gaza represents not an aberration but the quintessential expression of the West as a genocidal settler colonial project (Dabashi, 2025). Dabashi exposes the constitutive racism of canonical Western philosophy from Kant and Hegel to Habermas and Adorno, revealing how these thinkers provided the metaphysical cover for colonial violence while claiming universal moral authority (Dabashi, 2025). Second, it engages Nelson Maldonado-Torres's concept of combative decoloniality, which distinguishes between genuine decolonial praxis rooted in collective movements and decoloniality lite, the commodification of decolonization as academic discourse (Maldonado-Torres, 2025). Maldonado-Torres's critique of the civilization barbarism schema illuminates how this binary has justified genocide from the Americas to Palestine (Maldonado-Torres, 2025). Third, the paper incorporates Palestinian epistemic resources: the Nakba as foundational catastrophe, the refugee camp as the nomos of the colonial modern, and the poetry of Mahmoud Darwish as a counternarrative to Western philosophical nihilism. These frameworks are read alongside decolonial thinkers such as Frantz Fanon, Enrique Dussel, and Edward Said, who theorize liberation from the perspective of the colonized.
Research Methods	This study employs critical philosophical analysis and decolonial textual interpretation as its primary methodological approaches. Following Dabashi's method of reading against the grain, the paper analyzes canonical philosophical texts not as timeless wisdom but as historically situated discourses that have legitimized colonial violence. It also engages in what Maldonado-Torres calls movement generated thinking, theorizing not from the detached position of the academic but in solidarity with collective struggles for liberation. The method is essentially one of epistemic rupture: to read Western philosophy from the perspective of Gaza, to allow the rubble to become the site of theory, and to center the testimonies of the oppressed as valid epistemological sources.
Summary Findings	This study finds that liberal peace education, insofar as it remains anchored in Eurocentric philosophical traditions, reproduces the very logic of colonial violence it purports to overcome. The civilization barbarism schema that justified the conquest of the Americas, the transatlantic slave trade, and the Holocaust continues to operate in contemporary discourse that renders Palestinian life unworthy of moral consideration. However, the Palestinian experience generates alternative epistemological resources: the Nakba as a lens for understanding catastrophe, the camp as revealing the true nature of colonial modernity, and the poetry of Mahmoud Darwish as a mode of resistance that refuses both victimhood and nihilism. The paper further finds that Maldonado-Torres's concept of combative decoloniality offers a way forward: peace education must abandon decoloniality lite, the reduction of decolonization to academic fashion, and instead root itself in movement generated knowledge and transnational solidarity. Gaza emerges not merely as a site of suffering but as ground zero for a post-Western moral imagination, one in which peace is inseparable from justice and bearing witness is a categorical imperative.
Conclusion and Recommendation	This paper concludes that peace education after savagery requires a radical epistemological reorientation: learning to see from Gaza, to abandon the metaphysics of civilization that justifies barbarism, and to cultivate a planetary consciousness forged in collective struggle against the permanent war waged on racialized peoples everywhere. This demands that peace educators: 1. Provincialize Western philosophy by exposing its constitutive racism and refusing its claims to universality, treating it instead as one ethnocentric tradition among many. 2. Center Palestinian epistemology, the Nakba, the camp, the poetry of resistance, as a source of theoretical insight, not merely as evidence of suffering. 3. Adopt a combative pedagogy rooted in movement generated knowledge and transnational solidarity, rejecting the false neutrality that in the time of genocide becomes complicity. 4. Liberate the memory of the Holocaust from Zionist appropriation, connecting it to the continuum of colonial genocides and building shared moral ground between Jewish and Palestinian struggles for liberation. 5. Teach peace as inseparable from justice, not as liberal reconciliation between asymmetrical parties, but as the collective struggle against the structural violence of colonial modernity. In the final analysis, the classroom after Gaza must become a site of decolonial combat. Not because it chooses to be, but because in the time of genocide, neutrality is no longer possible.
Keywords	combative pedagogy, decoloniality, genocide, Palestine, peace education
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Religion, Justice and Peace
Education	Social Justice Education

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Reference Number	28
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Ly N.B. Le
Title	Buddhist Peace Education in Myanmar: Contributions and Challenges
Problem Statement	Myanmar has been experiencing the most intractable conflict in Southeast Asia. Religious communities in Myanmar have been active in offering peace education to the wider community as part of the solution to the conflict. Studies on faith-based peace education in Myanmar has been rare and even non-existent. This study fills in this gap.
Research Questions or Objectives	This study aims to examine the contributions and challenges of Buddhist peace education to building a just and inclusive society in Myanmar during the on-going conflict.
Literature, Concept and Theory	The study employs the 4Rs framework on sustainable peacebuilding in education (Lopes Cardozo et al., 2019) to analyze the case study.
Research Methods	The study used a qualitative case study approach to collect data which included documentary research and ethnographic fieldwork in Mandalay during February – March 2025.
Summary Findings	The study found that Buddhist peace education has made some contributions to promoting a just and inclusive society in Myanmar including distributing resources and access to peace education for the underprivileged communities, recognizing diversity, and promoting inclusivity and reconciliation. However, it also faces several challenges concerning the curriculum, program administration, quality control and the conflict-based problems.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The study gives recommendations on how to improve Buddhist peace education for sustainable peacebuilding in Myanmar.
Keywords	Buddhism, Peace Education, Myanmar, Contributions, Challenges
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	Yes, I have a doctorate, and I publish empirical social science papers.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Education, Religion, Justice and Peace
Education	Moral Education

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Reference Number	29
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Rey Ty
Title	Human Rights and Wrongs of the Hegemon: Political Economy, Social Justice, and Decolonial Perspectives
Problem Statement	The Founding Parents of the U.S. have contributed to ideas of freedom and democracy in the land which became the home of immigrants fleeing from persecution. However, recent events reveal a reversal of trends to violations of freedom of thought, conscience, liberty, and right to life.
Research Questions or Objectives	To match and identify 1) the respect for human rights and 2) violations of human rights in the past five years in the U.S.A. from the 3) political economy lens, 4) social justice lens, and 5) decolonial lens.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Current-events news reports from reputable international media and atest literature from the United Nations, reputable international human rights organizations, and Nobel laureates will be cited.
Research Methods	Thematic analysis of news and reports
Summary Findings	The U.S. has important contributions to the ideas of human rights in general. However, recent trends reveal there is a pattern of violations going on in the past five years. Political economy lens reveal a connection between wealth and power that impinges on the respect or violation of rights. Social justice perspective exposes unequal experiences of people of color, different social classes, and women. Decolonial lens explains the systematic discrimination, criminalization, and expulsion of both documented immigrants and undocumented migrants of color.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Citizens must be vocal about their concerns, call for policy actions at the local, state, and federal levels to respect human rights, campaign and vote for representatives who promote human rights for all.
Keywords	Civil Liberties and Rights, Decolonial Lens, Political Economy, Social Justice, U.S.
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	Yes, I have a doctorate, and I publish empirical social science papers.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Culture, Justice and Peace
Education	Social Justice Education

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Reference Number	30
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Rey Ty
Title	Realism and Liberalism in Hegemonic Foreign Policy: Political Economy, Decolonial, and Marxist Critiques
Problem Statement	US foreign policy flipflops between corporate globalization and the spread of democracy on the one hand and extending its global hegemony and economic nationalism on the other hand. Such is the international general crisis that affects the whole world.
Research Questions or Objectives	To identify US economic and political foreign policy action trends, to reveal the reasons for which the changes in US foreign policy from one administration to another take place, and to critique US foreign policy from the political economy, social justice, and decolonial perspectives.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Literature includes political realism, economic nationalism, hegemonic stability theory, liberalism, democracy, political economy, social justice, and decolonial lens
Research Methods	Sources are reputable news reports which are subjected to thematic analysis. An original comparative table matching all the keywords as evidenced in foreign policy practice viewed from political economy, social justice, and decolonial lenses.
Summary Findings	Both political realism and economic liberalism lead to global inequality, as big corporations and politicians benefit from either US foreign policy conservatism or liberalism.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Social justice and decolonial perspectives necessitate centering the people over profits, big corporations, and politicians.
Keywords	Decolonial Lens, Economic Liberalism, Corporate Globalization, Social Justice, U.S. Foreign Policy
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	Yes, I have a doctorate, and I publish empirical social science papers.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Culture, Justice and Peace
Education	Learning Theory

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Reference Number	31 / 33
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Palleti S Santhi Swaroop
Title	Children as Makers of Alternative Worlds: Family-Based Peace Education in a Culture of Violence
Problem Statement	In contexts shaped by consumerism, religious nationalism, and ideological polarization, children are often socialized into dominant narratives that normalize exclusion and violence. Peace education frequently overlooks the formative role of the family as a primary site of moral and social construction.
Research Questions or Objectives	This study argues that families, understood as world-making communities in light of Psalm 78, function as primary sites of child-centered peace education that cultivate critical resistance to dominant cultures of violence.
Literature, Concept and Theory	This study is informed by Walter Brueggemann's concept of the family as a counter-cultural world-making community, social construction theory, and contemporary peace education scholarship.
Research Methods	This study employs theological-hermeneutical analysis of Psalm 78 alongside conceptual analysis of family-based child moral formation within peace education frameworks.
Summary Findings	The findings indicate that when families intentionally cultivate shared memory, ethical responsibility, and hope, children develop critical awareness that resist dominant cultures of violence. This affirms the family as a primary site of child-centered peace formation and alternative world-making.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Peace education must intentionally strengthen families as child-centered world-making communities that nurture justice-oriented identities capable of resisting cultures of violence.
Keywords	child-centered education, family pedagogy, moral formation, peace education, world-making
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Religion
Education	Behaviorist Education

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Reference Number	32
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Jagoda Szargan
Title	Peaceful Governance: A Taoist Approach to Contemporary International Relations
Problem Statement	This paper explores the gap in the understanding of peaceful governance through the lenses of Taoism in contemporary international relations.
Research Questions or Objectives	The main goal is to answer the research question “How does the Taoist approach explain the peaceful governance in contemporary international relations?”
Literature, Concept and Theory	This study examines the major international relations theories, such as realism, liberalism, and constructivism, along with the concepts of the prisoner’s dilemma, complex interdependence, the world system, and power, analyzed through the lenses of Taoism.
Research Methods	The chosen research method is the qualitative source analysis of the relevant literature, concepts, and international relations theories.
Summary Findings	According to the Taoist approach, peaceful governance can be effectively maintained through: non-coercive action, as it reduces conflict escalation, strategic restraint, which allows the proportional defense rather than domination, and natural order, aligning with the existing systemic dynamics, which outlines the significance of diplomacy, mediation, and soft power to achieve peace.
Conclusion and Recommendation	To conclude, the Taoist approach integrated with the international relations theories provides the explanation of the peaceful governance in the contemporary international relations built on the non-coercive action, strategic restraint, and proportionality instead of coercive action, power expansion, and domination.
Keywords	Conflict, Governance, Peace, Power, Taoism
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Learning Theory

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Reference Number	34
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	REV WELLANE ANANDA THERO
Title	Humanistic Buddhism as a Framework for Sustainable Peacebuilding
Problem Statement	The research problem is the need to identify whether and how Humanistic Buddhism can provide a practical and holistic framework for sustainable peacebuilding by integrating personal transformation with social action.
Research Questions or Objectives	To examine how Humanistic Buddhism functions as a practical and holistic framework for sustainable peacebuilding by integrating inner moral transformation with active social engagement to address both personal and structural causes of conflict.
Literature, Concept and Theory	This study is informed by the principles of Humanistic Buddhism and by theories of positive peace and engaged spirituality that connect inner transformation with social responsibility and structural justice.
Research Methods	This study employs a qualitative textual and conceptual analysis of Humanistic Buddhist teachings and practices to examine their relevance for sustainable peacebuilding.
Summary Findings	The study finds that Humanistic Buddhism provides a holistic framework for sustainable peace by integrating inner moral transformation with active social engagement. It demonstrates that compassion, ethical responsibility, and community-based action effectively address both personal and structural causes of conflict, thereby supporting long-term social harmony and stability.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The study concludes that Humanistic Buddhism should be further developed and applied as an integrated ethical and practical model for promoting sustainable peace and long-term social harmony in contemporary society.
Keywords	Compassion, Humanistic Buddhism, Peacebuilding, Social Responsibility, Sustainable Peace
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Moral Education

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Reference Number	35
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Zar Chi Oo
Title	Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices of Conflict Resolution Skills among Myanmar Teachers, and students from Federal Schools since the 2021 Military Coup: Where We Are Now, What Is Working, and the Way Forward
Problem Statement	The purpose of this study is to conduct a critical assessment of Myanmar's current status in terms of the outcomes of peace education for both students and teachers, approximately four years following the coup.
Research Questions or Objectives	In order to critically evaluate the efficacy of peace education initiatives and identify evidence-based pathways forward, a comprehensive KAP assessment of conflict resolution skills among Myanmar teachers and students from federal schools since the 2021 military coup will be conducted.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Integrative Theoretical Foundations: Contact Hypothesis (Allport, 1954), Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977), Critical Peace Education (Freire), Trauma-Informed Pedagogy and Conflict Sensitivity Framework
Research Methods	Mixed method: quantitative KAP survey and KII interviews with teachers and students
Summary Findings	The following are preliminary findings of the knowledge, attitude, and practices of Myanmar teachers and students from federal schools based on program evaluations, grey literature, and practitioner consultations done in advance of this proposal. The empirical study will test, improve, and validate these findings. 7.1 Knowledge: General Knowledge, In-Depth Through training programs, online courses, and community workshops, a considerable number of Myanmar civil society actors, educators, and youth leaders have been introduced to conflict resolution concepts during the post-coup period. However, so far, it seems that this exposure has led to a basic understanding of terms like "mediation," "dialogue," and "de-escalation," instead of the deeper knowledge needed to use these ideas effectively in Myanmar's complicated conflict situation. There is a persistent gap between rural, conflict-frontline populations who have had little access to peace education but whose need for practical conflict resolution capacity is most acute, and urban-educated, CSO-affiliated populations who have received repeated training (and risk knowledge saturation without practice). 7.2 Attitudes: Changing, Divisive, and Politically Limited There have been significant changes in attitudes since the coup. Many people's attitudes toward conflict itself, particularly regarding acceptable forms of conflict response, have changed as a result of the almost universal public disgust at the military's brutality. Since the coup, many young Myanmar people who previously supported principled nonviolence have changed their minds, contending that in the face of repression on the scale of a genocide, armed resistance is not only morally necessary but also justified. This shift does not imply that the ability to resolve conflicts has been neglected. Instead, there is a growing recognition of the importance of solving conflicts at the community level in ways that save lives, like settling disputes between villages, easing tensions between militias and civilians, and handling resource conflicts in places where people have been displaced, even as trust in formal dialogue and state-led processes has fallen apart. Interestingly, opinions within interfaith networks and women-led organizations have been more consistent in favoring nonviolent methods, indicating that these communities of practice are especially crucial pillars for the sustainability of peace education. 7.3 Underground, Adaptive, and Undervalued Practices Since the coup, the military has either taken control of or stopped operating the official conflict resolution institutions and procedures that were in place, such as formal dialogue tables, complaint mechanisms, and grievance mediation channels. On the other hand, community-based and informal dispute resolution techniques have shown remarkable adaptability and resilience. Using local conflict resolution practices that predate both the current conflict and post-conflict programming, teachers and community elders still mediate local conflicts. Religious leaders have established safe forums for discussion within their communities. Peer mediation skills that are used in schools, displacement camps, and online communities have been developed by youth groups working through peace clubs and student networks. Because these practices are not institutionalized and purposefully avoid documentation for security reasons, they are frequently undetectable to external evaluations.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Peace education in Myanmar must be updated to reflect the post-coup political reality. This means developing frameworks that help participants analyze structural sources of conflict, understand the politics of dialogue and negotiation in authoritarian contexts, and build critical literacy about disinformation and manipulation. No peace education intervention will effectuate significant changes in knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) in Myanmar without first confronting the widespread trauma experienced by participants. Future programming should require MHPSS integration as a standard design element, not an optional add-on. This means training facilitators in trauma awareness, building referral pathways to mental health services, and designing program schedules that allow time for emotional processing.
Keywords	peace education, conflict resolution, knowledge, attitude and practices, Myanmar education, Myanmar federal schools
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
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General Area	Education, Justice and Peace
Education	Skills Development

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Reference Number	36
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Ranto Marbun
Title	Heavenly and Earthly Citizenship: The Boarding House (Indekos) Phenomenon only for Muslims in Yogyakarta.
Problem Statement	Why are there public boarding houses only for Muslims in Muslim-majority areas? Is an ID card not sufficient for citizens to reside in a country? As citizens.
Research Questions or Objectives	Earthly and heavenly citizenship are interrelated.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Pancasila, Ideologi, Civics, Heavenly and Earthly Citizenship
Research Methods	Using library methods and survey methods; surveys for collecting field data and literature for scientific discussion.
Summary Findings	Citizenship (civics) is not only a matter of state (world) but also religion (heaven)
Conclusion and Recommendation	Racism is our share challenge; our recommendation to review the state ideology that justifies racist acts.
Keywords	Boarding House (Indekos), Citizenship, Earthly, Heavenly, Muslim
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Religion, Justice and Peace
Education	Knowledge Dissemination

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Reference Number	37
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Moakumla Longkumer
Title	Traditional Institutions as Sites of Resilience and Mutual Construction for Indigenous Community-Based Peace Education
Problem Statement	In today's rapidly changing world, the relevance of traditional institutions is often underestimated, yet it acts as beacons and remains vital as custodians of cultural heritage, transmitting knowledge, values, and critical skills that sustain continuity and community resilience across generations.
Research Questions or Objectives	This study examines how traditional institutions function as sites of resilience and mutual knowledge construction in sustaining Indigenous community-based peace education.
Literature, Concept and Theory	This study is informed by Indigenous knowledge systems and community-based peacebuilding theories that understand traditional institutions as relational spaces of cultural transmission and social cohesion, resilience theory which explains how communities sustain continuity amid conflict and change, and the feminist liberation methodology of Elisabeth Schüssler Fiorenza, which critically examines power, gender, and inclusion while reconstructing institutions as participatory and justice-oriented sites of mutual knowledge construction.
Research Methods	This study employs qualitative research methods, including ethnographic fieldwork, semi-structured interviews, and contextual analysis, to examine traditional institutions as sites of resilience and community-based peace education.
Summary Findings	The findings indicate that traditional institutions function as active sites of resilience by transmitting cultural values, mediating conflict, and sustaining intergenerational continuity within Indigenous communities. They also demonstrate that these institutions facilitate mutual knowledge construction and participatory learning, thereby strengthening community-based peace education.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Traditional institutions should be critically engaged and inclusively revitalized as culturally grounded and participatory sites for strengthening Indigenous community-based peace education and resilience.
Keywords	Community-Based Peace Education, Indigenous Resilience, Mutual Knowledge Construction, Traditional Institutions, Women's Agency
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	Yes, I have a doctorate, and I publish empirical social science papers.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education
Education	Traditional Education

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Reference Number	38
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Ven. Pitawala Vimaladhamma Thero
Title	The Foundation of Inner Peace: A Buddhist Perspective on Self-Directed Learning and Global Harmony.
Problem Statement	This research addresses the misconception that global peace is solely an external socio-political construct rather than a result of individual moral education and inner liberty.
Research Questions or Objectives	The primary objective is to investigate how self-directed learning of Buddhist principles can foster individual inner peace to prevent societal conflict.
Literature, Concept and Theory	The study is informed by the classical Theravada Buddhist doctrine of mental development and contemporary theories of social justice education.
Research Methods	The study employs a qualitative analysis of traditional texts to understand the learning process of achieving internal peace.
Summary Findings	The findings reveal that sustainable peace is an internal state governed by the mind's self-regulation through formal and informal moral education.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The study recommends re-integrating internal peace cultivation into modern pedagogy to ensure long-term global stability.
Keywords	Buddhist Ethics, Global Harmony, Inner Peace, Moral Education, Self-Directed Learning
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education
Education	Moral Education

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Reference Number	39
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	BENJAMIN PELLEGRAM
Title	Transnational Christian Language Networks and Ethnolinguistic Maintenance in Northern Thailand
Problem Statement	Christian communities in Southeast Asia participate in expanding global religious networks that operate across linguistic boundaries.
Research Questions or Objectives	I am doing qualitative research. Scholarship on global Christianity emphasizes demographic shifts and transnational religious flows, less attention has been given to how language functions as infrastructure within these networks. English often operates as a global connective medium, particularly in theological education, missionary exchange, text and liturgy and digital communication.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Philip Jenkins (2002, 2006) describes demographic shift of Christianity toward the Global South and the rise of transnational religious networks; Andrew F. Walls and Lamin Sanneh (2023) emphasize Christianity's historical translatability, they argue argues that Christianity spreads through vernacularization rather than linguistic domination.
Research Methods	I am doing auto-ethnography
Summary Findings	English functions as a transnational bridge connecting Southeast Asian Christians to global networks and Minority Christian groups maintain indigenous languages as markers of ethnic continuity and communal autonomy. Therefore, Christianity contributes a layer of multilingual practices for some Christians in Northern Thailand.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Christian communities' language networks show both globalization and localization.
Keywords	Christianity in Thailand, Ethnolinguistic identity, Minority language maintenance, Linguistic capital, Transnational Language Networks
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Religion, Culture, Justice and Peace
Education	Flexible Learning

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Reference Number	40
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	BENJAMIN PELLEGRAM
Title	Interrupted Pathways and Reconstructed Futures: Refugee Students' Academic and English Language Needs in Higher Education
Problem Statement	Undergraduate students who are refugees often have interrupted educational trajectories, students who experienced a disruption in formal education, and have certain needs at their academic institutions.
Research Questions or Objectives	This is a qualitative study. The purpose is how to better serve students who are refugees with interrupted educational trajectories.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Dryden-Peterson (2023) examines interrupted education of refugee youth and offers pedagogical solutions for reconstructed futures. Htew (2023) studies Myanmar students in Thai universities in particular.
Research Methods	This is autoethnography.
Summary Findings	The study will offer some suggestions for helping these groups of students to navigate higher education. They may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • English language proficiency gaps • Classroom management/expectations • Institutional support. • Culturally informed Curriculum/Trauma Informed Pedagogy ' Peer and Faith Based Support and Mentoring
Conclusion and Recommendation	There are both institutional adjustments universities must make as well as classroom pedagogy teachers must make.
Keywords	Interrupted education, Higher Education, Southeast Asia, Reconstructed Futures, Applied Linguistics
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Religion, Culture, Justice and Peace
Education	Learning Process

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Reference Number	41
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	James Michael Suerte Felipe
Title	Integration of Human Rights in Teacher Education: Basis for Contextualized Multidisciplinary Human Rights Education Framework
Problem Statement	The aim of the study was to analyze how faculty members of the College of Education of Bataan Peninsula State University integrate Human Rights concepts into the teaching-learning process.
Research Questions or Objectives	The study sought to find what are the teaching methods, challenges, and opportunities that Faculty Members encounter in terms of integrating Human Rights in classroom instruction.
Literature, Concept and Theory	This study draws on theories such as Freire's Pedagogy of the Oppressed, Dewey's Progressive Education, and Sen's Capability Approach wherein Human Rights are seen as an integral part of Education in order to push towards a progressive society.
Research Methods	The study employed semi-structured interviews as the primary method while using observations, and document analysis was used to support the data gathered from the semi-structured interview.
Summary Findings	The findings identified that faculty members employ interactive, student-focused, such as the research identifies learner-centered strategies including case studies, dilemma questions, democratic classroom practices, and lectures, methods yielding opportunities for behavioral shifts, diversity embrace, and moral development, while challenges encompass student fixed mindsets from traditional schooling, lack of awareness, subject abstraction (e.g., in Mathematics), online engagement barriers, and absent institutional mandates for human rights integration, time allocation and contextual relevance.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The findings identified that faculty members employ interactive, student-focused, such as the research identifies learner-centered strategies including case studies, dilemma questions, democratic classroom practices, and lectures, methods yielding opportunities for behavioral shifts, diversity embrace, and moral development, while challenges encompass student fixed mindsets from traditional schooling, lack of awareness, subject abstraction (e.g., in Mathematics), online engagement barriers, and absent institutional mandates for human rights integration, time allocation and contextual relevance.
Keywords	Human Rights, Teaching Strategies, Human Rights Education, Higher Education Institution, Integrated Human Rights Education
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Education
Education	Humanist Education

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Reference Number	42
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Ven. Kelasa
Title	Cultural Conflict Resolution: A Critical Analysis of Non-Material Culture and Hybrid Peacebuilding Among Myanmar's Ethnic Groups
Problem Statement	Cultural diversity in Myanmar, while a potential national strength, currently leads to misunderstandings, discrimination, and violent conflicts.
Research Questions or Objectives	1) To categorize and analyze the influence of Non-Material Cultural factors that contribute to the formation and intensification of conflicts among Myanmar's armed organizations. 2) To critically evaluate the structural and social causes, such as colonial policies and religious intolerance, and to quantify the scale of societal fragmentation driven by cultural disagreement. 3) To examine the operational utility of the Hybrid Peace framework and synthesize it with empirically grounded indigenous conflict resolution practices, culminating in a detailed, phased implementation roadmap for peacebuilding stakeholders.
Literature, Concept and Theory	The following concepts and theories were used: Liberal Peace (Top-Down), Local Peace (Bottom-Up), and the Hybrid Peace model (Integrated), with the core analysis guided by the definition of Non-Material Culture (ideas, beliefs, values, language, and social norms). The conflict root causes were analyzed as a combination of ideological (Non-Material Culture) and structural factors (colonial policies, discrimination, religious intolerance).
Research Methods	This study is a conceptual, non-empirical study rooted in the humanities and philosophy. The research methodology employs Qualitative Data Analysis (QDA) of secondary academic and archival sources. Data collection was based entirely on a rigorous library search of published books and verified online resources. This included secondary data analysis for organizational fragmentation (45 EAOs and 57 political parties) and a specialized textual survey of the Buddhist Pāli Canon (suttas).
Summary Findings	1) The primary cultural factors driving the conflict are rooted in Non-Material Culture, specifically divergent ideas, beliefs, and values regarding governance, national identity, and group status (RQ1). 2) The scale of political fragmentation is profound, manifested in the existence of 42 Ethnic Armed Organizations and 57 political parties, driven by identity-based nationalism where extreme cultural love for one's own group prevents compromise (RQ2). 3) The Hybrid Peace model is validated as the optimal framework, as it integrates universal norms with local indigenous Buddhist ethics like Mettā and equanimity to maximize legitimacy and operational effectiveness (RQ3).
Conclusion and Recommendation	The conflict in Myanmar is fundamentally sustained by the destructive power of politicized Non-Material Culture and reinforced by historical structural injustices. The Hybrid Peace model, integrated with indigenous Buddhist ethics, is the optimal framework to transform cultural diversity from a primary source of division into a resilient foundation for unity.
Keywords	Culture, Conflict, Solution, Myanmar, Ethnic Groups
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Culture
Education	Skills Enhancement

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Reference Number	43
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Frederic Gloor
Title	Walking Together: Chiang Mai's Interfaith Pilgrimage
Problem Statement	In Chiang Mai, religious communities coexist without truly knowing one another, limiting opportunities for authentic dialogue and mutual understanding, despite a shared spiritual richness.
Research Questions or Objectives	To create a tangible space for encounter through interfaith pilgrimages, where ignorance of the other transforms into curiosity and human connection, drawing on local traditions and student participation.
Literature, Concept and Theory	This project is inspired by Leonard Swidler's three rules of interfaith dialogue (1983) as well as the tradition of pilgrimage in Theravāda Buddhism, where meditative walking and visits to sacred sites are central practices of transformation.
Research Methods	A 10-minute documentary captures the journeys, shared spiritual experiences, and participant testimonies, illustrating how walking and immersion break down ignorance more effectively than theoretical debates, highlighting personal stories that become collective narratives.
Summary Findings	The pilgrimages revealed that physical experience (walking together, sharing sacred spaces) and active listening dissolve invisible prejudices and create an ephemeral yet tangible community. The finalized video will serve as a tool to replicate this dynamic elsewhere and improve future editions by integrating participant feedback.
Conclusion and Recommendation	To deepen this impact, we must train youth and community leaders in interfaith listening, strengthen local community involvement in designing and leading pilgrimages, and document these experiences to create replicable models rooted in daily life. The goal is to shift from passive coexistence to active collaboration, driven by inclusive, grassroots initiatives.
Keywords	Community Connections, Cultural Exchange, Experiential Learning, Interfaith Dialogue, Peacebuilding Walk
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Religion, Culture, Justice and Peace
Education	Experiential Learning

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Reference Number	44
Types of Presentation	Attend Only
Name	Saw Franklin D. Aye
Title	The Relevance of 'Giving War a Chance' for Myanmar's Protracted Armed-Political Conflict
Problem Statement	The idea of 'Give War a Chance' has rarely been examined philosophically and normatively using Myanmar as a case study.
Research Questions or Objectives	To critically assess the explanatory relevance of 'Give War a Chance' in Myanmar's conflict, and the aim is not to defend and celebrate war and violence but to refuse false peace and protracted conflict.
Literature, Concept and Theory	The literature is mainly based on the argument or logic of Edward N. Luttwak (1999), and critiques from others.
Research Methods	Research methods are normative and philosophical reflection with contextual analysis, and qualitative, desk-based, non-human-subject research.
Summary Findings	The study demonstrates 'Give War a Chance' has explanatory relevance but lacks moral legitimacy as a peace solution, and provides a rigorous philosophical critique of war-based peace logic specifically applied to Myanmar's conflict.
Conclusion and Recommendation	This study argues that while the idea of "Giving War a Chance" is relevant for understanding why Myanmar's conflict persists and why peace efforts fail, it cannot justify war as a path to peace, and it is to rethink peace as an ethical and political project that refuses both false peace and protractedly violent solutions.
Keywords	Armed-Political Conflict, Justice, Myanmar, Peace, War
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Activist Education

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Reference Number	45
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Joenna Mae L. Dizon, Lovely Charm Jayne J. Antonio, Gabriel Elisha Lois T. Balmeo, Patrick L. Del Mundo, Kate P. Escudero
Title	Disability, Dignity, and Development: A Narrative of Change in Empowering Persons with Disabilities
Problem Statement	This study examines how participatory governance and local initiatives drive social transformation and empowerment for Persons with Disabilities in Mariveles, Bataan
Research Questions or Objectives	This research aimed to evaluate the extent of social inclusion and involvement, access to services, and policy and institutional support experienced by PWDs, while also assessing the role of participatory governance in their empowerment.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Participatory Governance Theory stipulates that democratic government has to move beyond formal representation to incorporate direct citizen participation in decision-making.
Research Methods	Qualitatively, semi-structured interviews were conducted with eight purposely selected key informants, including PWD leaders and municipal officials, and analyzed using the Most Significant Change (MSC) technique.
Summary Findings	Findings indicate that while the municipality demonstrates moderate progress in providing programs and institutional support, PWDs continue to face barriers such as inaccessible infrastructure, gaps in rehabilitation and livelihood services, incomplete data systems, and limited meaningful participation in local governance.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The study concludes that although the locale has established important foundations for disability inclusion, sustained institutional strengthening and participatory mechanisms are necessary to achieve transformative outcomes. It is recommended that the local government enhance accessibility compliance, improve registry and monitoring systems, expand inclusive livelihood and rehabilitation programs, and institutionalize stronger participatory platforms for PWD representation in decision-making processes.
Keywords	disability inclusion, empowerment, local government, most significant change, participatory governance
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
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Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Justice and Peace
Education	Skills Acquisition

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Reference Number	46
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Ryan Pecson
Title	Advocacies of Ayta educators in catapulting language and cultural heritage among IP schools and local communities
Problem Statement	Ayta educators, as cultural workers, bearers, and ambassadors, play a pivotal role in promoting and sustaining the Indigenous language and culture in the school and the community. In the advent of technological and societal developments, Ayta teachers' advocacies ramified contextualized and immersive education integral for cultural survival.
Research Questions or Objectives	The study echoes the advocacies of ten purposively selected Ayta educators from three provinces in Region III, Philippines in promoting language and cultural heritage among Indigenous Peoples (IP) schools and local communities through the lens of descriptive phenomenological research.
Literature, Concept and Theory	This study is anchored on Critical Pedagogy by Paulo Freire, as it frames Ayta educators' advocacy for Indigenous rights, cultural survival, and community empowerment through transformative and dialogic education.
Research Methods	Semi-structured one-on-one interviews are used to gather data upon securing consent forms and endorsements, wherein the results are analyzed using Descriptive Phenomenological Analysis (DPA).
Summary Findings	The findings indicate that Ayta educators contextualize their lessons through localization and indigenization, infusing Indigenous Knowledge, Systems, and Practices (IKSP) in the curriculum. They also actively engage their IP and non-IP learners in the Indigenous month celebration through presentations and immersions, inviting IP elders to share their knowledge, demonstrate, and perform. They also teach their language, culture, and rights (IPRA Law) to IP and non-IP learners, as well as to younger and older generations who seem to forget their cultural identity. They also develop Indigenized learning materials in teaching the Ayta language and culture.
Conclusion and Recommendation	As intermediaries, Ayta educators can bridge the gap between education and cultural preservation, serving as voices for both IP learners and the communities through constant calls for the establishment of language and cultural centers for future generations. Through these advocacies, Ayta educators take a stand and cement their legacies both in academia and the communities they represent – a reminder of their triumphs in long-standing battles for IP representation and education.
Keywords	Advocacies, Ayta Educators, Indigenous Language, Indigenous Culture, IP Schools
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	Yes, I have a doctorate, and I publish empirical social science papers.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Education
Education	Community Education

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Reference Number	47
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Bhikkhu Kotte Upananda
Title	Compassion, Ethical Restraint, and Mental Training: Counseling Dimensions in the Sallekha Sutta
Problem Statement	How the Sallekha Sutta provides a canonical framework for understanding authentic counseling grounded in mental purification and ethical transformation.
Research Questions or Objectives	This study argues that the Sallekha Sutta presents an authentic model of mental purification and ethical transformation that should ground contemporary Buddhist counseling in original canonical teachings.
Literature, Concept and Theory	This study is informed by early Buddhist canonical theory of mental purification and self-effacement as presented in the Sallekha Sutta of Majjhima Nikaya and supported by the ethical and psychological framework of the Pāli Canon.
Research Methods	This study employs a qualitative textual and doctrinal analysis of the Sallekha Sutta within the broader context of the Pāli Canon.
Summary Findings	The study finds that the Sallekha Sutta presents mental purification as a systematic process of abandoning unwholesome states and cultivating wholesome qualities rooted in self-effort and mindfulness. It further demonstrates that authentic Buddhist counseling must be grounded in careful study of original canonical sources to preserve ethical integrity and doctrinal accuracy.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Therefore, contemporary Buddhist counseling should remain firmly grounded in careful study of the Sallekha Sutta and other original canonical sources to ensure authenticity and ethical depth.
Keywords	Buddhist Counseling, Educational Development, Mental Purification, Moral Education, Self-Directed Learning
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Religion
Education	Mental Development

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Reference Number	48
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Saw Zadkiel Eh-Kwee
Title	Blessing the Regime or Bearing the Cross: Issue-based Polarization of Elite Christian Leaders in Post-Coup Myanmar
Problem Statement	Polarization erodes churches' collective moral authority and undermines their credibility as advocates for democracy, human rights, and peace, as the junta can cite silent Christian voices while dissenting leaders and communities face marginalization, oppression, or persecution, in current conflict context.
Research Questions or Objectives	1) To identify and describe the types of stances in the public statements and communications of elite Christian leaders and church bodies in post-coup Myanmar emerge toward the military junta. 2) To examine how leaders ideologically and rhetorically frame their alignments/engagements, reshaping the churches' moral authority, internal relationships, and public credibility. 3) To explore the reasons why particular leaders and institutions adopt their stance positions in this context
Literature, Concept and Theory	1. Religion, Secularism, and Peace Process Framework- (Hayward & Frydenlund, 2019) 2. Ambivalence of the Sacred - (R. Scott Appleby, 2003) 3. Polarization Theory - Peter T. Coleman et al. (2021) 4. Cognitive Dissonance Theory - (Varlaro, 2025) Leon Festinger (1957) 5. Ideological Positioning- (Nilsson & Jost, 2020)
Research Methods	Study used narrative review research design, analyzing academic and grey literatures, reports and publications from reputable institutions and websites, to gather information supporting the objective of the study.
Summary Findings	1) Elite Christian leaders and institutions in post-coup Myanmar grouped into three main stances: pro-military, anti-military, and ambivalent. 2) Findings explain the stances are articulated through distinct theological and rhetorical repertoires, intensifying the unholy order and obedience. 3) Findings reveal the interacting shaping factors such as historical relationships with state power, perceived vulnerability to repression, ethnic and institutional identities, and dependence on junta-linked resources.
Conclusion and Recommendation	This study underscores the pro-military polarization of elite Christian leaders through their public statements and communications.
Keywords	Elite Christian Leaders, Myanmar, Post-coup, Issue-based Polarization
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
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Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Religion, Justice and Peace
Education	Moral Education

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Reference Number	49
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Thi Ha Xuyen Pham
Title	Community Education and Preservation of Sea Deity Worship among Coastal Residents in Sam Son city, Vietnam
Problem Statement	Urbanization and tourism development in Sam Son are reshaping and institutionalizing community education processes that strengthen the preservation of sea deity worship among coastal residents.
Research Questions or Objectives	Community education embedded in sea deity worship functions as a key mechanism for transmitting spiritual knowledge and reinforcing cultural identity in Sam Son.
Literature, Concept and Theory	This study is informed by social learning theory, primarily developed by Albert Bandura, to interpret sea deity worship as a culturally embedded process of community education in Sam Son.
Research Methods	This study employs ethnographic fieldwork, including in-depth interviews and participant observation.
Summary Findings	The findings indicate that sea deity worship in Sam Son operates as a culturally embedded form of community education rooted in village structures and further strengthened and institutionalized through urbanization and tourism development.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The preservation of sea deity worship in Sam Son should prioritize community agency and village-based education alongside urban and tourism development strategies.
Keywords	Community education, Coastal residents, Sea Gods, Urbanization, Village Structures
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Culture
Education	Community Education

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Reference Number	50
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	BENJAMIN PELLEGROM
Title	Religion and English Language Motivation: A Mixed Methods Study in Northern Thailand
Problem Statement	Second language (L2) motivation research has emphasized, intrinsic motivation, as well as economic and cultural elements of motivation. In L2 motivational theory, religion and religious identity are less examined
Research Questions or Objectives	This is a mixed methods study about how religious commitment and identity are related to language learning, The study shows how students with religious identities and commitments tend to have stronger language learning motivation.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Dornyei (2013) discussed the link between the commitment of faith and the commitment and investment of language learning.
Research Methods	This is a explanatory sequential mixed methods study.
Summary Findings	Religious identity plays a significant role in shaping English language motivation among students in Northern Thailand. Learning English is not only important academically and economically but also for spiritual and faith community reasons.
Conclusion and Recommendation	This shows that religion can play a role in language learning
Keywords	Language Learning Motivation, Religion and Language, Applied Linguistics, Northern Thailand, Religious Studies
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Religion, Culture
Education	Experiential Learning

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Reference Number	51
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	SUMANDAL, HENMHARK
Title	The Lived Experiences of Persons with Physical Disability on Public Transportation
Problem Statement	Public transportation systems in the Province of Bataan remain inaccessible and inadequately responsive to the mobility needs, dignity, and rights of persons with physical disabilities despite existing legal mandates and modernization efforts.
Research Questions or Objectives	This study aims to explore and interpret the lived experiences of persons with physical disabilities in accessing public transportation in Bataan in order to identify barriers, coping strategies, and context-based recommendations for inclusive mobility.
Literature, Concept and Theory	This study is informed by the social model of disability and rights-based accessibility frameworks, particularly as articulated in United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and Republic Act No. 7277, which emphasize inclusive mobility as a fundamental human right.
Research Methods	This study employs a qualitative narrative inquiry design using in-depth semi-structured interviews and thematic analysis to examine the lived experiences of persons with physical disabilities in public transportation
Summary Findings	Findings reveal that persons with physical disabilities in Bataan encounter persistent physical, social, and attitudinal barriers in public transportation, particularly inaccessible vehicle design and inconsistent driver support. Despite these challenges, participants demonstrate resilience through adaptive coping strategies and propose practical, context-based recommendations to improve inclusive mobility.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Local governments and transport providers must enforce accessibility laws and adopt universal design and disability-awareness measures to ensure safe, dignified, and inclusive public transportation for persons with physical disabilities.
Keywords	Accessibility, Disability, Mobility, Public Transportation, Resilience
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Experiential Learning

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Reference Number	52
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Nokchanaro Jamir
Title	The Practice of Ceremonial Feasting among the Ao Nagas: A Socio-cultural approach to Peacebuilding
Problem Statement	The essence of sharing is one of the main components in Ceremonial feast. However, the significance and the traditional practise of feast had been lost with the advent of modernization in the community.
Research Questions or Objectives	The research seeks to understand the socio-cultural approach of feast as an initiative for peacebuilding strategy for inter and intra conflicts.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Culture and identity influence peacbuilding relationship (Lederach, 1995; Avruch, 1998; Brauchler, 2015). Cultural identities frequently serve as a sources of values, beliefs and narratives to promote peace. Local practice and practical wisdom can be used as a resource as a model of peacemaking when people understand their cultural heritage and self-aware of it. (Lederach, 1995).
Research Methods	The research is mainly based on descriptive method
Summary Findings	The practice of Ceremonial Feast serves as a social justice that demand all people have a share in the wealth of land. When there is inequality, we cannot expect peace and harmony in the community.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The traditional practise of Ceremonial feast in the community help to prevent the growth of capitalism and the control by few people
Keywords	Ao Nagas, Ceremonial feast, Education, Peacebuilding,
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Culture
Education	Social Learning

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Reference Number	53
Types of Presentation	Attend Only
Name	Hsu Pan Naing
Title	Beliefs and Memory: Myanmar Buddhist and Muslim Women's Daily Practices to Peace in Thailand
Problem Statement	Buddhism is the majority religion in Myanmar, while Islam is a minority faith. Since independence in 1948, power imbalances between the Buddhist majority and Muslim minorities have deepened, worsening further after 2021. Despite religious differences, women from both communities share common social structures shaped by patriarchy, everyday religious life, and memory, which influence their identities and lived experiences.
Research Questions or Objectives	Qualitative research
Literature, Concept and Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Burmese Book - Everyday Economic survival in Myanmar by Ardeth Maung Thawngmung 2018. ● Buddhism and Islam - Comparison and Dialogue by See Hoon Peow ● Making Peace with Faith by Garred Abu-Nimer ● Other books - recommend by Dr Rey
Research Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Qualitative research ● Informal Dialogues ● Participatory Action Research Method (PAR)
Summary Findings	Women's memories and daily religious practices as quiet forms of everyday peace Women use religion to memory as coping strategies and discipline to deal with fear, loss, displacement, and uncertainty in everyday life Beliefs and daily practices became more significant to help women in everyday peace during crisis
Conclusion and Recommendation	Community and cultural programs should acknowledge women's informal peace-building roles through religion and beliefs.
Keywords	Buddhism, Muslim, Myanmar, Memory, Daily Practices and Peace
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Culture
Education	Behaviorist Education

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Reference Number	54
Types of Presentation	10-minute max NON-Academic Presentation
Name	Lea Gentile
Title	An International Language as a Requisite for Global Civilization, examining Unifon, an English Phonetic Alphabet
Problem Statement	English as used today is impractical as a choice for a universally adopted international language for its currently used spelling irregularities.
Research Questions or Objectives	Make a strong case for the consideration of Unifon as a revised practicable spelling system for English.
Literature, Concept and Theory	English could become a more suitable option for an international language, a spiritual foundational principal for humanity's future as mentioned in the sacred writings of Bahá'u'lláh, by adopting a one-to-one spelling sound/writing system.
Research Methods	Unifon will be presented through video, explanations, demonstrations and poetry, that reflect pedagogical advancements and enhanced language teaching methodologies.
Summary Findings	The one-to-one relationship of sounds to symbols in Unifon facilitates oral skills acquisition of English with minimal interference from native language phonemes and has advantages over the currently used international phonetic alphabet.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Unifon, a 40-character alphabet to write the 40 sounds of the English language in a one-to-one relationship, is proposed as a modification of the current spelling of English for speaking and writings skills enhancement making it more accessible, practicable and functional for all levels of international communication.
Keywords	pedagogy, pedagogical advancements, skills acquisition, skills enhancement, teaching methodologies
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	No.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Education, Religion, Justice and Peace
Education	Classroom Learning

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Reference Number	55
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Sa George Eikhant
Title	Interfaith Dialogue in Multi-Religious Communities: A Catholic Perspective from Myanmar
Problem Statement	Myanmar is a religiously diverse country where religion shapes social life, but differences have often led to tension and conflict.
Research Questions or Objectives	To explore how the Catholic Church in Myanmar, inspired by the teaching of the Catholic Church and the Documents of the Second Vatican Council, promotes interfaith dialogue and peaceful coexistence in multi-religious communities in Myanmar.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Interreligious Dialogue (Nostra Aetate, 1965) 2. Peace building (Catholic Social Teaching, Pacem in Terris by Pope John XXIII - 1963) 3. Social Harmony and Common Good (Bishops of the Vatican II, 1965) 4. Dialogue of Life (Dialogue and Proclamation, 1991) 5. Islam, Buddhism, and conflict in Myanmar by Kyaw N. N. (2016) 6. Catholic Bishops' Conference of Myanmar (CBCM). (1965-2023) 7. Karuna Mission Social Solidarity (KMSS). (2001-2019) 8. Myanmar Council of Churches (MCC). (1995-2020) 9. Social Friendship (Fratelli Tutti by Pope Francis 2020)
Research Methods	The study uses a qualitative research approach with informal dialogue, document analysis, and field observations as much as possible
Summary Findings	In Myanmar, Karuna Mission Social Solidarity (KMSS) and Church social programs promote interfaith dialogue by bringing people of different religions together through social work, meetings, and peacebuilding activities to build relationships and cooperation.
Conclusion and Recommendation	I come to realize that local community initiatives are an effective way to promote real dialogue and peacebuilding.
Keywords	Catholic Church, Interfaith Dialogue, Myanmar, Peacebuilding, Religious Diversity
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	Yes, I have a doctorate, and I publish empirical social science papers.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Religion
Education	Traditional Education

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Reference Number	56
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Rey Ty
Title	Political Economy, Biopolitics, and Political Psychology of Conservative and Progressives on Conflict and Peace
Problem Statement	Society is divided between conservatives and progressives on almost all economic, political, cultural, religious, and social issues in the political economy of countries.
Research Questions or Objectives	1) From biopolitics and political psychology, why are conservatives and progressives differ in their stance on almost all issues in the political economy of societies? 2) What are the trademarks of conservative thought based on biopolitics and political psychology? 3) What are the trademarks of progressive thought based on biopolitics and political psychology? 4) How can the gap between conservative and progressive thought be bridged?
Literature, Concept and Theory	Literature used includes discussions on biopolitics, political psychology, political economy, conservatism, progressivism.
Research Methods	This article is based on document analysis, many of which are peer reviewed articles, meta-analysis, and meta synthesis of conservative and progressive political psychology.
Summary Findings	1. Different parts of the brain are triggered that lead to more conservative or more progressive thought. Both nature and nurture play a role. 2. Conservatives favor status quo, stability, and strong leaders. 3. Progressives are open-minded, flexible, and open to change. 4. The gap between conservatives and progressives can be bridged by phrasing key positions that signal both continuity for conservatives and change for progressives. For example, "tax the rich (a progressive call) so that everyone is treating equally and fairly (appeal to both conservatives and progressives) and that the ordinary family in rural areas and cities can have affordable medical care."
Conclusion and Recommendation	Peace studies and Peace education can promote both social order and social change by understanding biopolitics and political psychology and applying that knowledge for use in actual conflict situations.
Keywords	Biopolitics, Conservatism, Political Economy, Political Psychology, Progressivism
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join the Editorial Board?	Yes, I have a doctorate, and I publish empirical social science papers.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Culture, Justice and Peace
Education	Activist Education

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Reference Number	57
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Rey Ty
Title	Political Economy of Finance, Corporate, and AI Capital Broligarchy: The Death of and Saving Democracy
Problem Statement	There is a contradiction between capitalism and democracy. An oligarchy controls markets, platforms and information, while people lose their privacy and democracy.
Research Questions or Objectives	RQ1: What are the features of brologarchy today? RQ2: What are the causes of the rise of brologarchy? RQ3: How can the people win back their privacy and democracy in opposition to the brologarchy?
Literature, Concept and Theory	Brologarchy, finance capital, platform capitalism, AI capital, surveillance capitalism, democracy
Research Methods	This research employs qualitative research design. Facts and figures are collected from publicly available data from 2000 to 2026. The U.S. at the macro level of analysis is the main case under scrutiny.
Summary Findings	RQ1: The characteristics of brologarchy in the U.S. are the following: BlackRock, Vanguard, and State Street dominate finance capital. Amazon, Apple, and Google are platform monopolies. NVIDIA, OpenAI, and DeepMind have concentrated AI power. Meta and Google are surveillance systems. All these brologarchic capitalists capture the state through lobbying networks. RQ2: Some of the cause of the rise of brologarchy are: neoliberal deregulation, capital accumulation, network effects and scale economies, financial crises consolidation, and technological centralization. RQ3: For the people to win back political and economic power away from oligarchy, the following are required: transparency, accountability, regulation of AI, antitrust, and equal taxation of oligarchs.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Finance capital, big tech, and AI converge, which lead to greater inequality and reduced democracy.
Keywords	Brologarchy, Democracy, Finance, Corporate and Tech Capital, Inequality, Surveillance Capitalism
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join the Editorial Board?	Yes, I have a doctorate, and I publish empirical social science papers.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Justice and Peace
Education	Activist Education

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Reference Number	58
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Rey Ty
Title	Political Economy, Biopolitics, and Political Psychology Comparative Analysis of Conservative-Liberal Spectrum
Problem Statement	Societies are becoming more and more polarized across the ideological spectrum. There are fragmented and oversimplified explanations in different disciplines, such as biology, economics, political science, and psychology. This article investigates the multidimensional spectrum of explanations of the conservative-progressive spectrum.
Research Questions or Objectives	RQ1: How are political economy, biopolitics and political psychology distinct yet related? RQ2: Why do conservative and progressive ideologies differ from the political economy, biological, and psychological perspectives? RQ3: How can the conservative-progressive divide be bridge?
Literature, Concept and Theory	Concepts that guide this article include biopolitics, political psychology, political economy, and related subtopics, including neuroscience, personality, and institutions.
Research Methods	This qualitative article utilizes the qualitative research design. It rests on pragmatic and critical realist research paradigm to provide insights into real-world conflictual situations. Research strategy involves the employment and triangulation of previously conducted meta-analysis and meta-synthesis in peer-reviewed journals. Cross-discipline convergence of data serves as triangulation for accuracy.
Summary Findings	RQ1: Biopolitics refer to macro-level governance of people. Political psychology deal with micro-level cognition and emotion. Political economy examines power and wealth. The integration of all reveals their interaction. RQ2: Based on peer-reviewed meta-studies, ideologies differ due to biology (genetic influence, brain difference), psychology (personalities, moral frames), and political economy (inequality, economic insecurity). RQ3: The conservative-progressive gap can be bridged but not eliminated through: economic (increased equality; inclusive growth), political institutional (electoral reform, win-win), psychological (bias awareness, intergroup dialogue).
Conclusion and Recommendation	Multiple factors (biology, psychology, political economy) affect ideology
Keywords	Biopolitics, Conservatism, Ideology, Political Economy, Political Psychology
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join the Editorial Board?	Yes, I have a doctorate, and I publish empirical social science papers.
General Area	Education
Education	Activist Education

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Reference Number	59
Types of Presentation	10-minute max NON-Academic Presentation
Name	Nay Hein Phyo
Title	Barriers to Peace Education in Karenni Internally Displaced Persons Contexts
Problem Statement	In Karenni State (Kayah State) of Myanmar, the educational landscape has significantly declined due to the escalating conflict that began in 2021. The military coup, which emerged from a civil war, has forced thousands of families to escape. Karenni State experiences one of the highest rates of displacement in the nation (OCHA, 2024). Many children currently reside in Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) camps and are educated in makeshift learning environments. These facilities are primarily constructed from bamboo and tarpaulin, offering very limited infrastructure. Peace education is particularly needed in this context of violence. Such education focuses on imparting values such as tolerance, dialogue, respect, and non-violent methods of resolving conflicts.
Research Questions or Objectives	1. What types of barriers exist to the implementation of peace education in Karenni IDP education settings? 2. How do these barriers influence the teaching and learning of peace-related values and skills in classroom practice? 3. Why do these barriers occur and persist within the Karenni IDP education context?
Literature, Concept and Theory	Peace Education Theory (Lynn Davies 2004), Education in Emergencies (EIE 2023 UNICEF), Documentary Research/Document Analysis Theory (Glenn A. Bowen 2009), Conflict and Education Disruption Concept (Myanmar Education Consortium 2021), Humanitarian Crisis and Displacement Framework (UNOCHA 2024).
Research Methods	This was documentary research design in which news articles, books, and NGO reports were used to gather data. (review literature, secondary data, documents, thematic analysis Reflexivity: Ethics, “Etic” (cultural outsider)
Summary Findings	Summary of Findings RQ1 (Types of Barriers) The foremost barrier is the perennial physical insecurity of attacks, a critical shortage of teaching materials and unqualified volunteer teachers who have no specialist skills to lead peace-building discussions. RQ2 (Implications for Practice): Teacher attention to simplistic literacy and numeracy priorities (i.e. lack of time, available resources) instead of an appropriate focus of peace education; trauma among students is deeply rooted and is linked to underperformance of emotional responses as well as in cooperation needed for peace initiatives. RQ3 (Why): There are persisting obstacles due to the ongoing conflict, a continuous deficiency in humanitarian financing of education unlike food and medicine, and crumbling infrastructure to a limited extent in remote IDP camp sites.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Conclusion Peace education is of great importance for Myanmar’s future but it cannot be established to its full extent. Without robust support resources like teacher training and consistent support funding – peace education for children in transition will remain a dream, not a reality we have now. Recommendation : NGOs /Local Stakeholders should train camp teachers specifically on peace education and conflict resolution. Schools should have mental health counseling, so that students can heal from traumas before learning about peace. Humanitarian donors need to invest more into education based on the premise that education is a life-saving intervention. International NGOs should work more directly with local Karenni school groups to produce materials relevant to their culture.
Keywords	Conflict, Displacement, IDPs, Peace Education, Karenni State
General Area	Education
Education	Educational Development

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Reference Number	60
Types of Presentation	10-minute max NON-Academic Presentation
Name	DANDJESSO Gaétan
Title	Peace Education program: case study of YSP Benin in universities and schools
Problem Statement	We are dealing with Terrorism, religious intolerance and family issues who are affecting the youth, the non-civic engagement of the youth
Research Questions or Objectives	Why Peace Education for human Development: Essence, Principles and goals
Literature, Concept and Theory	Peace Ambassadors' Network of the Universal Peace Federation
Research Methods	Video, interview
Summary Findings	Peace Education program curriculum
Conclusion and Recommendation	Peace Education program is absolutely needed if we want our kids to become better peacemakers tomorrow
Keywords	Human development, Living for others, 4 Steps of love, Vision for global and sustainable peace
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Religion
Education	Pedagogy

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Reference Number	61
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Saw Lalbwel Htoo
Title	EXPLORING THE CHINA'S POLITICAL INTERVENTION IN CHINA-MYANMAR BILATERAL ECONOMY IN 2026
Problem Statement	China's 2026 political actions, including the endorsement of junta elections, are creating an imbalanced economic relationship that may undermine Myanmar's long-term economic sovereignty.
Research Questions or Objectives	What are the specific forms of Chinese political intervention currently affecting the Myanmar bilateral economy in 2026? How do China's political intervention impact critical economic sectors, such as the China-Myanmar Economic Corridor (CMEC) and extractive industries in 2026?
Literature, Concept and Theory	Bilateral economy, China's political intervention, Dependency Theory; Great-Power Trap
Research Methods	Qualitative Content Analysis (QCA)
Summary Findings	China uses diplomatic recognition of the junta and border enforcement as tools to manage the internal conflict in Myanmar. Interventions have forced the relocation of gem trade to Chinese territory and accelerated the construction of the Muse-Mandalay railway.
Conclusion and Recommendation	1. Implement policies to diversify international trade partners; .2. Strengthen legal protections for local natural resources.
Keywords	Bilateral economy, China-Myanmar relations, Extractive Industries, Political Interventions
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
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Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Justice and Peace
Education	Knowledge Acquisition

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Reference Number	65
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Sa Nehru
Title	Youth Agencies in Social Change in Myanmar Post-Military Coup
Problem Statement	The role of youth agencies is essential part of the social change in Myanmar post-military coup
Research Questions or Objectives	The study focuses on the qualitative study design to explore the role of youth agency in the post-coup in Myanmar setting and which comprises gathering, analyzing data from various academic works.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Three themes of literature guide this article: youth in Myanmar context, social change and post-military coup
Research Methods	The study focuses on the qualitative study design to explore the role of youth agency in the post-coup in Myanmar setting and which comprises gathering, analyzing data from various academic works.
Summary Findings	Youth agency promotes alternative education, driving social movement, and active citizenship in social change in Myanmar military coup.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Change agents and faith-based organizations, INGOs and governments should promote and provide the culture of youth agency in Myanmar context and for strengthen in social change.
Keywords	Myanmar, Post-military coup, Social change, Youth, Youth agencies
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
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Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education
Education	Behaviorist Education

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Reference Number	66
Types of Presentation	10-minute max ACADEMIC Paper Presentation
Name	Fr. Sa George Eikhant, Ven. Kelasa, Khine Myo Linn
Title	Interfaith Cooperation for Child Protection: Reflections from an International Conference in Asia
Problem Statement	Isolated religious efforts often lack the systemic coordination needed to address complex, cross-border child protection issues effectively.
Research Questions or Objectives	1) To identify interfaith programs at the 2026 Chiang Mai conference; 2) To analyze coordination mechanisms among religious leaders; 3) To evaluate the necessity of interfaith networks.
Literature, Concept and Theory	This study utilizes the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) and the theory of "Shared Moral Responsibility."
Research Methods	This study used a qualitative ethnographic research design, employing participant observation and reflective analysis during the March 2026 conference.
Summary Findings	1) Activities included interfaith prayers and thematic workshops; 2) Leaders collaborate through spiritual solidarity and joint advocacy; 3) Networks are essential for addressing multi-dimensional challenges.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Protecting children is a shared moral and spiritual mandate that transcends religious boundaries, requiring sustained inter-religious cooperation. Institutionalize interfaith child protection committees and develop community-based interreligious dialogue programs.
Keywords	Child protection, Conference, Ethnography, Interfaith cooperation, Religious leaders
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Religion
Education	Behaviorist Education

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Reference Number	67
Types of Presentation	10-minute max NON-Academic Presentation
Name	Khine Myo Linn
Title	Strengthening Community Peace through Interfaith Dialogue and Collaborative Actions in Rakhine State after 2021 Coup
Problem Statement	Armed conflicts cause mistrust among the communities.
Research Questions or Objectives	1) To examine interfaith dialogue and collaborative actions in strengthening community peace in Rakhine state after 2021 coup. 2) To examine how interfaith dialogue and collaborative actions build trust and social cohesion in strengthening community peace in Rakhine state after 2021 coup. 3) To analyze why interfaith dialogue and collaborative actions are effective in strengthening community peace in Rakhine state after 2021 coup.
Literature, Concept and Theory	Manual Inter-religious dialogue (Allan Kalafa Kefa and Ombuge. M. Moses, 2012) Let's talk: Practical Pointers for Inter Faith Dialogue (The interfaith network for the UK, 2017) Interreligious conflict and the politics of interfaith dialogue in Myanmar (Nyi Nyi Kyaw, 2019) Armed Conflict → Communal Disharmony → Interfaith Dialogue → Cultural Action → Reduced Prejudice → Trust-building → Social Cohesion → Community Peace
Research Methods	Documents and reports review, informal observation from networks
Summary Findings	1) To increase community peace through interreligious visits, food exchange programs, cultural exchange events, peace tree planting and joint activities. 2) To support the trust-building by dialogue sessions and collaborative actions. 3) To maximum the positive impacts and sustainable peace, reduce mistrust, intercommunal tension and stop hate speech.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Interfaith dialogue and cultural exchange activities are effective of peacebuilding strategy in conflict-affected community, Rakhine State.
Keywords	Community Peace, Exchange activities, Interfaith Dialogue, Social Cohesion, Trust-building
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Religion, Culture
Education	Skills Development

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Reference Number	68
Types of Presentation	10-minute max NON-Academic Presentation
Name	Rey Ty
Title	Peace under the Imperial MAGA Presidency: In Search of Forever Enemies?
Problem Statement	Peace is viewed differently within factions under the MAGA presidency. There is no systematic mapping of the ways in which specific personalities and factions operationalize peace.
Research Questions or Objectives	RQ1: What is peace within the conservative factions? RQ2: Why do conservative factions differ? RQ3: How is peace achieved by each faction? RQ4: How does each faction compare to theory?
Literature, Concept and Theory	Seminal work on conservatism includes works of Burke (1790/2009), Smith (1776/2003), Kant (1795/2006), Hobbes (1651/1996), Morgenthau (1948/2006), Griffin (1991), Paxton (2004), Mudde (2007), and Müller (2016). Key literature on peace emerged from Galtung (1969) and Ikenberry (2011).
Research Methods	This research resorts to the qualitative, deductive, comparative approach. Data were derived from secondary sources and public discourses in mainstream and social media up to April 2016. The strategy employed was the thematic classification of the different factions within the conservative party during the MAGA presidency as of 2016.
Summary Findings	RQ1: The spectrum from the conservative right to left are: monoculturalism, morality, sovereignty, no war, no coercion, strength, democracy, trade, and institutional or system stability. RQ2: Factions differ because they have different mechanisms to attain peace: exclusion, tradition, borders, non-intervention, minimal state, military strength, intervention, trade, and institutions. RQ3: In relation to theory, there are the different conservative models for peace: restraint, nationalism, libertarianism, deterrence, neocon regime change, neoliberal trade, establishment of institutions, and moral order.
Conclusion and Recommendation	MAGA conservatism is hybrid, not monolithic, and covers several contending peace theories. There are disagreements on how peace is achieved. Fragmentation reveals divergence in policies.
Keywords	Conservatism under MAGA, Neocon, Neolib, Populism, Peace
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. More than one session is fine.
Join the Editorial Board?	Yes
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Culture, Justice and Peace
Education	Social Justice Education

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Reference Number	69
Types of Presentation	10-minute max NON-Academic Presentation
Name	Sa George Eikhant
Title	Catholic Church Teaching on Dialogue and Fraternity: From Vatican II to Today
Problem Statement	While Catholic documents since the Second Vatican Council promote dialogue and fraternity, their practical effectiveness in overcoming religious intolerance remains contested.
Research Questions or Objectives	This study examines how Catholic Church teaching since the Second Vatican Council promotes dialogue and fraternity and evaluates its impact on interreligious relations today.”
Literature, Concept and Theory	This study is informed by Catholic ecclesiology and interreligious dialogue theory as articulated in documents of the Second Vatican Council and subsequent Church teachings.
Research Methods	This study employs qualitative document analysis to examine key Catholic teachings on dialogue and fraternity from the Second Vatican Council to contemporary texts.
Summary Findings	The study concludes that Catholic teaching promotes dialogue and fraternity, but real-world application remains limited in some contexts.
Conclusion and Recommendation	The study recommends strengthening the practical implementation of Catholic teachings on dialogue and fraternity in diverse contexts.
Keywords	Catholic Church Teaching, Dialogue, Fraternity, Interreligious Relations, Second Vatican Council
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Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Religion
Education	Teaching Methodologies

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Reference Number	70
Types of Presentation	10-minute max NON-Academic Presentation
Name	Sa Nehru
Title	Christian Youth Leaders in Promoting Social Peace in Myanmar: Roles, Challenges and Opportunities
Problem Statement	Even though Christian youth leaders in Myanmar are actively engaged and advocating for social peace in various ways, they still face many challenges. These include a political crisis, limited resources, and restrictions from institutions. Additionally, a lack of understanding about their specific roles, effectiveness, and the obstacles they encounter makes it difficult to develop targeted strategies to support these young leaders as key actors to social peace in Myanmar. As a result, the advancement of social cohesion in Myanmar continues to be slow and remains uncertain.
Research Questions or Objectives	To examine the roles of Christian youth leaders in promoting peace in Myanmar. To identify the key challenges and opportunities in promoting peace in Myanmar. To recommend strengthening strategies for Christian youth leaders
Literature, Concept and Theory	Social peace (Pierre Bourdieu, 1986) Religious peacebuilding framework. (John Pual Lederch (1997) Transformative leadership (James MacGegor Burns, 1985)
Research Methods	The study focuses on qualitative research through thematic analysis to identify key themes, patterns, and insights from interview transcripts and focus group discussions, and research collaborators interview to gather the deep insights of their roles, challenges and opportunities in promoting peace in Myanmar.
Summary Findings	The findings highlight that Christian youth leaders are playing crucial roles in shaping their communities through various significant contributions. Furthermore, it is essential for these leaders to strengthen their strategies to effectively promote social peacebuilding.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Faith based organizations, INGO, CSOs should provide Christian youth leaders for capacity-building programs to strengthen youth-led peace initiatives. For a long-term run, they should support projects or grant aid for youth. Christina youth leaders should cooperate with the youth networks, CSOs, religious interfaith organizations
Keywords	Christianity, religious leaders, role, social peace, transformational leadership
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Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Religion, Justice and Peace
Education	Social Learning

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Reference Number	71
Types of Presentation	10-minute max Academic Paper Presentation
Name	Steven Rogers
Title	The Impact of Cultural Capital and Experiences of Undocumented Latino Students Enrolled in an US University
Problem Statement	It would be useful to explore the experiences and vastly understudied cultural capital of undocumented immigrants at the university level who led lives that are both mysterious and positioned as subaltern. The concept of subaltern emphasized “the fundamental relationships of power, of domination and subordination” (Sarkar, 1984, p. 273), the term came to mean a “space of difference” (Spivak, 2005, p. 476).
Research Questions or Objectives	1.) What are undocumented immigrant students’ expectations regarding their educational experiences? 2.) What cultural capital does undocumented immigrants bring to the university context and how does that prepare/not prepare them for their educational experiences? 3.) What meaning/significance does attending university have for these students? 4.) How can these experiences be described using the construct of critical race theory? 5.) How does the lack of legal immigration status impact the lived experiences of a select group of Latin@ students at one institution of higher education?
Literature, Concept and Theory	This literature review will first examine cultural capital and its relevance to undocumented Latina/o individuals. The study will then discuss the different definitions and theories of culture and then define the history and makeup of cultural capital with its roots stemming from French Sociologist Pierre Bourdieu. It will then have an extensive section that first discusses the history and makeup of Critical Race Theory and then focuses on the Latino/a branch of Critical Race Theory, Latino/a Critical Race Theory (LatCrit). A motif of having autonomy over one’s destiny is entrenched in critical race theorists (Ladson-Billings & Tate IV, 2006), and this is a question being explored in this study as it applies to undocumented Latino/a college students.
Research Methods	This paper will be in the form of a narrative review.
Summary Findings	Cultural capital, as it relates to educational information or knowledge of educational options and strategies for academic achievement, is also referred to as academic capital (St. John, Hu, & Fisher, 2011). “Teachers, it is argued, communicate more easily with students who participate in elite status cultures, give them more attention and special assistance, and perceive them as more intelligent or gifted than students who lack cultural capital” (DiMaggio, 1982, p. 190).
Conclusion and Recommendation	The cultural capital that undocumented university students possess should be respected and understood by what it has to offer society by the dominant culture.
Keywords	cultural capital, Critical Race Theory, Latino, Pierre Bourdieu, Undocumented students
Are You Willing to Co-chair?	Yes, gladly. For one session.
Join the Editorial Board?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	No.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	No.
General Area	Education, Religion, Justice and Peace
Education	Social Learning

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Reference Number	72
Types of Presentation	10-minute max Academic Presentation
Name	Rey Ty
Title	From Liberal to Decolonial Peace Education
Problem Statement	The hidden curriculum of the dominant model of peace education is liberal. It is Eurocentric in epistemology and marginalizes the knowledge of the Global South. This amounts to epistemic violence against the Global South.
Research Questions or Objectives	RQ1: What are the epistemology and pedagogy of decolonial peace education (DPE)? RQ2: Why does coloniality continue in peace education? RQ3: How does DPE affect learning outcomes? RQ4: What policies promote DPE?
Literature, Concept and Theory	Literature in this critical study includes themes related to critical pedagogy (Freire, 1970), peace education requiring justice (Kester, 2017), critique of colonial epistemology (Mignolo, 2011), and political economy of peace education (Novelli & Smith, 2011).
Research Methods	The qualitative research strategy is review of existing literature, analyzing themes, investigating Global South, including conflict-affected contexts. The ethics call for epistemic justice for the Global South.
Summary Findings	RQ1: The epistemology of DPE includes epistemic justice and plural knowledge, while its pedagogy is based on critical pedagogy and contextual curriculum. RQ2: Coloniality continues due to epistemic dominance of the Global North, structural inequality, curriculum control, market economy, and cultural hegemony. RQ3: The impact of DPE on learning outcomes are: critical consciousness, agency, justice orientation, intercultural competence, conflict transformation, and affirming indigenous and local identities. Case studies include conflict-affected Maori Aotearoa, Colombia, Mindanao in the southern Philippines, and South Africa. RQ4: Effective policies include curriculum reform, teacher training, participatory governance, adaptation to local contexts, and institutional support.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Conclusion: DPE requires long-term implementation, further research, and impact evaluation. The results of DPE include epistemic justice, social justice, locally relevant curriculum in conflict contexts, and critical pedagogy that promotes thorough social transformation. Recommendations: Policies need to institutionalize decolonial curriculum. Practitioners require training in critical and decolonial pedagogy. Further studies are needed to provide evidence-based and data-driven evaluation of the long-term impact of DPE.
Keywords	Epistemic Violence, Decolonial Peace Education, Liberal Peace Education, Peace Education, Political Economy
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Join the Editorial Board?	Yes
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education
Education	Humanist Education

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Reference Number	73
Types of Presentation	10-minute max Academic Presentation
Name	Benjamin Pellegrum
Title	Religion as a linguistic motivator at an EMI program at a Christian University in Thailand
Problem Statement	Most English Medium Instruction (EMI) at higher education focuses on English as a global language but overlooks how language learner motivation is related to broader sociocultural contexts and shaped by domain-specific language practices.
Research Questions or Objectives	RQ1. How do students' vision of their future selves, particularly those shaped by religious beliefs, influence their motivation to learn English? RQ2. How do students navigate educational, religious, and community linguistic domains and how does this process influence their language learning?
Literature, Concept and Theory	English as a Global Language - (Blommaert, 2010) English Medium Instruction (Baker, 2018) Language Motivation and Vision (Dornyei, 2019) Education for Displaced Students (Dryden-Peterson, 2023) Language Domains (Fishman, 1972) and (Qian, 2026) Global Christianity and Language Networks (Sanneh, 2003)
Research Methods	Ethnography and linguistic mapping
Summary Findings	Many students at an EMI have layered multilingualism, where English and local languages coexist through the domains of academic, social and faith communities. English is a resource for global mobility. The motivation for language learning and negotiating linguistic repertoires allow students to negotiate their immediate belonging and future vision across socio-linguistic and religious domains.
Conclusion and Recommendation	Language motivation in EMI is shaped by the intersection of global English, religious and ethnic communities.
Keywords	Language motivation, English Medium Instruction (EMI), Refugee education, Global English, Religious and ethnic identity
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Join the Editorial Board?	No
Are You Willing to Volunteer?	Yes, gladly.
Are You Willing to Volunteer to Take Photos or Videos Onsite or Online?	Yes, gladly.
General Area	Education, Religion, Justice and Peace
Education	Moral Education